

**GLASS CEILING FACTORS AFFECTING WOMEN'S
CAREER ADVANCEMENT IN PUBLIC SECTOR OF
NEPAL**

A Thesis

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
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Post-Doctoral Fellow

by

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2022

DECLARATION

I, **Dr. Dipak Mahat** declare that this thesis, entitled “**Glass Ceiling Factors Affecting Women’s Career Advancement in Public Sectors of Nepal**” submitted for the award of the degree of **Post-Doctoral Fellow** of this University, has not been submitted earlier for the award of any degree or diploma of this or any other University.

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This is to certify that entitled Glass Ceiling Factors Affecting Women's Career Advancement in Public Sectors of Nepal submitted by Dr. Dipak Mahat to SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY for the award of the Post-Doctoral Fellow is a Bonafide record of the research work carried out by him under my supervision and guidance. The content of the Report, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other institute or university for the award of any degree or diploma, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements by the Author.

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ADVANCEMENT IN PUBLIC SECTOR OF NEPAL By Dr Dipak
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.....
Dr. Dipak Mahat

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Chapter One

Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Since time immemorial, all of the most important labor market indices have consistently shown that the labor market is skewed in favor of men, regardless of where you live (Oppong & Kendie, 2017)[1]. The most contentious issue in the last 10 years has been the under-representation of women in most leadership and decision-making positions. Behavioral discrimination, wage and benefit discrimination, internal politics, unfair promotion and development possibilities, and some unwritten societal conventions restrict female involvement in activities long regarded to be the sole province of males are all examples of workplace hurdles (Begum & Sarker, 2018)[2]. This situation is referred to as a "ceiling" because advancement is impeded by it, and as "glass" (translucent) since the limitation is not obvious and is often an unwritten and informal rule (Afza & Newaz, 2008)[3]. These kinds of hurdles exist both internally, as a "glass ceiling" that makes it difficult for women to advance to the top levels, and externally, as a disincentive that keeps women out of male-dominated, higher-paying, and higher-status jobs (Khuong & Chi, 2017)[4]. The glass ceiling makes it difficult for women to advance in their careers and hinders them from working in male-dominated or regulated environments (Tiwari, Mathur, & Awasthi, 2019)[5]. For scholars; the subject of "what keeps women from rising to the top" has become a major concern.

1.2 Statement of Research Problem

"Working women" has been a major issue of conversation and organizational strategy since the beginning of the century (Sposito, 2013)[6]. Over the past century, the issue of how many women are in top management has emerged as a major research issue, which has resulted in a number of conferences and workshops aimed at highlighting women issues and how they are contributing to the world at large, though women still trail their male counterparts (Ayub, Khan, & Khushnood, 2019)[7]. In relation to the problem, the following research questions were posed. How Demographic factors Impact women's Career advancement?

What are the barriers that stop women from career development in higher administration position? What is the Perception of women employees towards glass

ceiling factors in relation to career advancement? What are the potential ways to break class ceiling?

1.3 Significance of the study

Women were in the past and are now finding it difficult to resist the injustices that exist in the job and in the household. Despite the fact that the company and government have implemented a number of rules, there is extremely little representation of female employees at the top. As a result, it is critical to investigate women's workplace engagement, professional progress, and organizational efforts to increase their opportunities for promotion. It is also necessary to emphasize the representation of women executives at various levels of the organizational hierarchy, the opportunities and limitations for women's advancement within the organization, and organizational initiatives promoting women's inclusivity by reducing women's perceived barriers within and outside the organization that may act as a barrier to their professional growth.

1.4 Research Objective

- 1 To analyze the role of demographic factors on women's career advancement,
- 2 To examine the perceptions of women employees towards glass ceiling factors in relation to career advancement,
- 3 To identify the barriers that stop women from advancing to higher-level administration roles,
- 4 To explore the effective model to break class ceiling.

1.5 Research Hypothesis

H₀₁ There is no significant relationship between societal factors and career advancement

H₀₂ There is no significant relationship between the personal factors and employee advancement

H₀₃ There is no significant relationship between the working environment and employee advancement

H₀₄ There is no significant relationship between the organizational factors and employee advancement

H₀₅ There is no significant relationship between the family factors and employee advancement

1.6 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

1.7 Limitations of the Study

1. This Study address only five factors (Social, personal, working environment, organizational and family) limiting the study to few independent variables only.
2. This study was limited to Public Sectors of Nepal only so it may vary in comparison to Private organization in terms of Glass ceiling.
3. The study's conclusions was represent the perspectives of the Ministry, Department, Agencies and State owned organization hence cannot be presumed to be universally relevant to all enterprises (Dike, 2013)[8].
4. The study was not confining to a particular sector, the results may alter when a sector-specific study is conducted.

5. A mixed methods approach was used; time management will be an issue in doing this study thoroughly.

1.8 Operational Definition

Glass Ceiling: Unseen able blockage in women career with name of various regions

Career Advancement: ascending path of an employee's professional trip

Managerial Women: Women who work in manager position

Public Sectors: Institution establish to serve citizen with earning maximum profit

Chapter Two

Review of Literature

2.1 Theoretical Review of Glass Ceiling

A "glass ceiling" is a metaphor for an impenetrable wall that presents a significant obstacle for women working their way up through the ranks of any organization's structure and preventing them from reaching the most senior leadership positions (Malhotra, Malhotra, & Jolly, 2022)[9]. Perales and his friends explain the "glass ceiling" as the obstacles that women experience while pursuing executive jobs. Many women with high levels of education and professional ability are prevented from reaching the same levels of leadership and responsibility as their male counterparts because of these often-invisible barriers (Yagüe Perales, Pérez Ledo, & March Chordà, 2021)[10].

The term "glass ceiling" was coined by Marilyn Loden during the 1978 Women's Exposition in New York. Between 1991 and 1996, the US Department of Labor conducted research on the issue and the impact it had on women and people of color in the workforce via the Glass Ceiling Commission (Ganiyu, Oluwafemi, Ademola, & Olatunji, 2018)[11]. Every woman manager who considers herself successful and is unable to advance in the business world may employ the "glass ceiling" notion. When women are encouraged to work in business environments, yet their potential is not fully realized, this concept is born (Purcell, MacArthur, & Samblanet, 2010)[12].

2.1.1 Role of demographic on career advancement

Demographic aspects and instructors' promotion intentions were studied. 226 male and 274 female instructors eligible for promotion were sampled. This research found that gender moderates the link between independent and dependent factors. Teachers in Malaysia will seek for promotion if others expect them to do so (Assim, Janis, Yaccob, & Jusoh, 2020)[13].

The study purpose is to examine the effect of demographic characteristics on career advancement in China's state-owned businesses and the link between promotion system and enterprise benefits. More than 6,500 human resource records from China's SOEs were analyzed. The findings give a theoretical reference for business promotion indicator selection and assist executives understand the effect of promotion on firms and people (Zhang, Lv, Yuan, Ren, & Wang, 2020)[14].

The research examined the effect of demographic characteristics and family-related constraints on women managers' career growth in Malaysian government-linked firms. This quantitative investigation employed a correlation study. Study consist 466 respondents, representing Malaysian government women managers. Job level, age, marital status, highest academic degree, and family-related restrictions affect women managers' career advancement (Subramaniam, Arumugam, & Akeel, 2014)[15].

Workers are regarded the most valuable asset of the business, and therefore the corporation must recognize and understand the wants and viewpoints of the employees towards their career in order to keep them in the organization. Career development is defined as the dynamic interaction between the emergence of an individual's own career identity and the expansion of one's professional relevance in the eyes of others. We wanted to see what effect a person's job path had on their personal characteristics, which is why we conducted this research. Documentary, exploratory, and descriptive research designs are all used in the study (Rajeswari & Mallika, 2013)[16].

2.1.2 Perception towards glass ceiling factors on career advancement

There are many variables that affect employee retention, the following main variables are explained below: Social Factors, personal factors, working environment, organizational factors, and family factors.

Effect of social factors on career advancement

The study looked at the work environment and social challenges that restrict women's rise to senior management. Purposive sampling was used to choose 100 women professionals from 500 in Pakistan's business sector. Social variables (0.298) were the most significant in predicting women's professional empowerment, according to the model (Khurshid, Naseer, Khurshid, Khokhar, & Irfan, 2022)[17].

Study conducted in Nigeria with an aim to examine the glass ceiling's impact on women's careers. Personal, relational, organizational, and cultural aspects were examined on women's professional progression. Self-administered questionnaire used for 480-person sample. Inferential and descriptive statistics were used to look at the data. The results show that the glass ceiling has a small negative effect on women's job growth. Personal, organizational, and cultural aspects also impact women's career advancement. This research finds that the glass ceiling hinders women's careers (Fapohunda, 2018)[18].

The study examined the marginalization of women in top leadership and management roles at Pakistani institutions, focusing on societal impediments to their appointment. According to a research, social limitations encourage professional segregation by gender. Ignorance about women's equal rights makes people unwilling to promote women. Without a shift in attitudes and societal mindsets, women's standing won't rise. Senior women's impressions of the challenges they experienced may help promote change (Raja, 2015)[19].

A research was done to find out what elements affect an employee's career advancement inside the company. An empirical inquiry is carried out to determine the impact on career development of employees in the Islamabad and Rawalpindi social environments of Pakistan's banking industry. To verify the proposed link between the variables, a general linear model is utilized. According to the study, social variables have a favorable impact on career development (Samim, 2015)[20].

Effect of Personal Factors on career advancement

Study is being done to determine how the glass ceiling affects how women grow their careers in Sri Lanka's construction sector. As part of a quantitative study, a group of 53 women in middle management were given a structured questionnaire. Results show a somewhat favorable association ($r=0.399^{**}$, $p 0.01$) between individual variables and women's career progress. Individual factors were identified using regression analysis's findings, and these elements have favorably impacted career growth (Alwis & Rathnayake, 2020)[21].

Identify the variables that affect nursing staff career advancement in Port-Said government hospitals. The design was descriptive correlation. The research found that personal characteristics (68.9%) have an impact on nursing career advancement. Personal aspects (nurses' personal behaviors, satisfaction, empowerment, and career development practices) and nursing career growth showed a statistically significant positive link (Mohammed, Wahab, & Ibrahim, 2020)[22].

According to the study, some factors impede women's job growth opportunities. The sample comprises of 57 female workers from various IT organizations in middle and senior management positions. Regression is run in sections to identify the factors that influence professional advancement the most. Personal traits are shown to have a correlation coefficient of 75.24 percent. Women's job progress is impacted significantly (Azeez & Priyadarshini, 2018)[23].

This research studied the effect of individual characteristics on career advancement prospects under radical organizational transformations including downsizing, mergers, and acquisition. 199 bank workers in a large city in South-Western Nigeria completed a questionnaire. The analysis of covariance, which accounted for variables, indicated substantial disparities in the career progression prospects of individuals with low and high self-efficacy. Personal development initiative levels did not affect professional growth chances. Self-efficacy beliefs and personal development initiative interact to impact professional growth potential. When self-efficacy beliefs are strong, career growth prospects are higher regardless of personal growth effort. Results are discussed (Okurame, 2014)[24].

Effect of working environment on career advancement

A research on Pakistan is being done to ascertain the relationship between the workplace and societal obstacles that prohibit women from climbing to top organization positions. The questionnaire that was utilized for the research was found to be reliable and valid by experts (0.704-0.982 Cronbach's alpha coefficient). The work environment (0.411) seemed to be the most significant factor influencing women's empowerment in terms of career advancement, according to the model's standardized regression coefficients (Khurshid, Naseer, Khurshid, Khokhar, & Irfan, 2022)[17].

Study was conducted to evaluating a worker's work environment and professional growth. To test this hypothesis, 70 Ministry of Primary, Secondary, and Vocational Education staff completed a questionnaire. A favorable work environment favorably promotes the growth of Ministry of Primary, Secondary, and Vocational Education workers, according to this investigation (Ouyi, 2019)[25].

Quality Work life and professional growth were studied in Hamadan, Iran. The 2013 structured surveys were based on input from 307 randomly chosen professors from two Hamadan public institutions. The patch analysis indicated that work life and career progress are positively associated ($\beta=.28$, $P=.039$) (Parsa, Idris, Samah, Wahat, & Parsa, 2014)[26].

Understanding how the workplace affects women's careers in (IT). The research looked at women's IT career satisfaction and why they prefer or detest their jobs. Participants said organization politics hampered their careers. In many cases, research participants had trouble complying with organizational rules, fitting in, adjusting to the organization's culture, and knowing whom to contact for help. Several participants

had trouble establishing the organization's informal power structure due to men-dominated political structures and networks (Wentling & Thomas, 2007)[27].

Effect of organizational factors on career advancement

This study aimed to identify which organizational characteristics affect employee career intentions. The sample size was 60 examinees (n = 60). Twenty significant Croatian organizations joined. Direct surveying was used. Applying regression analysis, Organizational elements that impact employee career progression are regressed. Analysis and enrichment of work has the largest influence on workers' career plans, followed by psychological monitoring. Career workshops and charts had the lowest r-squared (gusic, 2019)[28].

Study is focused on defining the need, examining its degree of intensity, and examining how important career development for workers is to an organization's performance. This research examines how learning organizations assist people's careers as they go through their own developmental stages. Employee performance is a dependent variable, whereas organizational support for career growth and supervisory support are independent factors (Saleem & Amin, 2013)[39].

The study investigates the relationship between women's views, job satisfaction, and psychological health at work and the perceived prevalence of organizational measures to support career advancement. 286 managerial and professional women at a prominent Turkish bank responded (72%). Negative views about women, equitable treatment, support, professional hurdles, and masculine norms were studied. Women who had favorable organizational experiences were more invested in their jobs and had higher levels of satisfaction and well-being (Burke, Koyuncu, & Fiksenbaum, 2006)[30].

A study examined the link between support, development, and commitment. Data were obtained at a large Midwest hospital. Managers and supervisors attending Managers as Coaches were invited to take out the survey. 262 supervisors and managers answered to the survey in eight seminars. Result displays the organizational support were substantially connected with career development in a large Midwestern hospital (Tansky & Cohen, 2001)[31].

Effect of family factors on career advancement

Study examines whether lack of mentorship, perceived organizational support, and family obligations affect women's reported professional success in the Indian IT industry. 292 individuals were surveyed using a standardized questionnaire. SEM was

utilized to investigate the influence of these obstacles on women's job achievement. The research found that each independent variable affects women's perceived professional success, signaling to women executives that they must overcome these obstacles to progress their careers (Chauhan, Mishra, & Bhakri, 2021)[32].

The study intentions to discover the impact of family obligations on women's career choices and the sort of work-life assistance they need from their employers. The survey includes 121 women from government, public, commercial, and NGO sectors. Findings revealed that family responsibilities impact women's careers. The female partner usually handles household responsibilities. Women professionals believe that child care impedes advancement (Buddhapriya, 2009)[33].

The research tests three hypotheses for family's impact on careers: choice, performance, and signaling. In a sample of American PhD graduates, family effect on job outcomes was felt at entrance, early and middle career phases. All arguments were supported. Two family characteristics, the existence of a small kid and not having a non-employed husband, were related with women choosing work-family balance in occupations, which predicted regional employment limits. Family structure didn't affect men's work choices. In later professional phases, women didn't profit as much as males by having a non-working husband. Women had a professional disadvantage since they were less likely to have non-working husbands, who were linked to high ranks by middle career for both genders (Kirchmeyer, 2006)[34].

Using a longitudinal design, researchers (Time 1, n=3555; Time 2, n=2339) analyzed how different types of family involvement influenced managerial careers. Both men and women's management performance and job disruption are predicted by family arrangement. Single fathers and childless singles both have slower job progress than others. Traditional fathers in the private sector had more managerial promotion, but post traditional moms progressed as much as other women. Male and female advancement was not impacted by family structures, but it was by the occupational field (Tharenou, 1999)[35].

2.1.3 Major Barriers in Career Advancement

Investigating professional barriers for rural women in India, the research collected data twice. First, qualitative data from 10 rural women was examined using thematic analysis. Second, quantitative data from 148 rural women was collected using a semi-structured survey questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS. Research showed 85% of

rural women are stifled by gender norms and overwhelmed with family duties (Khan, 2022)[36].

A research was done to examine the challenges and concerns of inequality faced by female faculty members at work and how they handled them. 20 female professors working at both public and private institutions in Karachi, Pakistan, were interviewed in-depth as part of the research using purposive and referral sample methods. According to the study's results, the biggest obstacles to women's job progression include a lack of family support, conventional culture, and gender stereotypes (Zaidi, 2022)[37].

Examine how gender stereotypes and social-cultural ideas affect women's professional development at a Tanzanian institution. This quantitative study surveyed 300 female university employees. The research uses Pearson correlation and multiple regression to test the hypothesis and uncover relationships. The research found that gender stereotypes hinder women's job advancement. Social-cultural views have little impact on women's job growth hurdles. This outcome is plausible for Tanzania, an inclusive and open country (Mwalyagile, 2020)[38].

Women in Yerevan, Armenia, face obstacles to job progression. The intended audience consists of Yerevan, Armenia, female workers in management and advanced positions. The glass ceiling effect, work-life conflict, and corporate culture are the three obstacles that are being looked at. A survey approach is employed in this quantitative research to gather numerical data from 102 respondents. The results showed that women's job development in Armenia was significantly impacted by the "glass ceiling" effect. The impact of work-life balance issues and corporate culture, however, differed from the findings of earlier research. This research has various real-world applications. Organizations should pay attention to the still-present effects of the glass ceiling and take action to combat prejudices against professional advancement (Marina, Singh, & Ahmad, 2021)[39].

The research explored Nepali women's professional hurdles. Two-phase research analyzed career advancement hurdles as seen by Nepali women workers to construct a 22-item questionnaire used to assess how 114 women managers regarded such barriers. We also tried to determine whether the perceived restrictions were position-, job-, or organization-specific. The survey found that sociocultural barriers impacted the professional advancement of Nepali women workers most (Adhikary, 2016)[40].

Article investigates career advancement literature and women's management progression hurdles. 15 women IT professionals were interviewed for the literature review. Gender stereotyping, work culture, lack of mentors and role models, work-family tensions, and lack of girls' informal networks explain Indian women IT workers' slowdown rise to management (Verma, 2011)[41].

2.1.4 Model to Break Glass Ceiling

To break through the barrier of the glass ceiling, Shonna suggests the following three steps:

1. Boost your professional network,
2. Participate in prejudice and stereotype education,
3. Promote your own interests (Waters, 2022)[42].

Six steps are suggested by a study from West Sydney to combat the Glass Ceiling in the Corporate World:

1. Aspiring female executives must make sure they have the necessary business knowledge and abilities,
2. Women must try to go into line management in regions with a majority of males. Again, leaving the cozy management service "ghetto," where many have taken refuge, is necessary,
3. Women need to try to get experience via "apprenticeship" and "acting" jobs,
4. Women should make an effort to get as much career counseling as they can,
5. For experience and a stronger visibility, women should volunteer for leadership and executive posts,
6. It would be very beneficial for women to learn how to gauge their productivity at work (Still, 1992)[43].

The removal of cultural and environmental barriers, the early identification of high-potential minority and female employees, and the implementation of leadership development programs that place an emphasis on lateral moves, line experience, and meaningful assignments rather than one-time training events have all been found to be effective strategies for shattering the glass ceiling. When examining corporate efforts to address this problem, Catalyst has discovered that it is helpful to differentiate between the various programs and policies that come under the work/family umbrella and those that are more explicitly geared toward women's business growth (Catalyst, 1993)[44].

Two friends did a study to find the Breaking the glass ceiling: chance for the organization to show the Strategies to overcome the glass ceiling in the supplied figure.

Figure 2 Model to Break Glass Ceiling by Sahoo and Lenka

Source:(Sahoo & Lenka, 2016)[45].

2.2 National and International Study

Study was conduct to find out what the major cause of the Glass Ceiling is and how it affects women's professional advancement. Individual, familial, organizational, and societal variables all influence the growth of career women. This study used quantitative research to obtain data from 100 Malaysian respondents through the distribution of questionnaires. SPSS by IBM, version 25 the data was assessed using software. The results show that family and organizational variables have a significant impact on women's career progress (Hussin, et al., 2021)[46].

The study in Oman with goal is to figure out what variables contribute to the glass ceiling and how it affects women's job progress. Data was gathered by a snowball sampling strategy, in which questionnaires were delivered to female employees in both private and public Oil and Gas organizations. The sample comprises of 180

people. SPSS 26 software was used to show and analyze the data, including independent T tests, crosstabs frequency distribution, and cluster bar graphs. According to the examination of the data gathered, private sector employees face glass ceilings in some areas more than public sector employees in others (AlZadjali, AlYahmadi, AlZakwani, AlAjmi, & Porkodi, 2020)[47].

When Indra set out to find out whether there was any correlation between the prevalence of the "glass ceiling" (GC) and women's professional advancement in Nepalese commercial banks, they discovered that there was. A total of 144 female branch managers from various branches were included as the study's sample. To determine the outcome of quantitative data, statistical procedures such as Pearson correlation and regression analysis were used. The findings demonstrated that GC exists in Nepalese commercial banks, as well as a negative association between GC and WCD, as well as the influence of the corporate climate on WCD (Shrestha, 2019)[48].

Bijaya investigate the impact of the glass ceiling on women's job advancement in Pokhara Metropolitan City banks. The female employees were chosen for this survey, which had a sample size of 99. The Cronbach's alpha test was used to determine reliability, and the result was 0.727, indicating that the data is closest to reality. The most influential aspect in the glass ceiling, according to the report, is sociocultural barriers. As a result, female employees must labor in order to overcome societal restrictions. Women employees are less likely to take higher positions due to difficulty balancing home and work duties, as well as a lack of family support. Financial institutions are encouraged to engage in initiatives that promote a healthy balance between work and family life (Lama, 2019)[49].

The goal of this study is to discover the elements that lead to women's professional development being hampered by the glass ceiling. An online survey is used to acquire information from women working in Indian IT companies. The sample consists of 57 female workers in middle and senior management roles from diverse IT companies. Although women's self-conceptions and management's perceptions of women obtaining higher positions also have a role, sociocultural factors impede women's progress the most, according to the study's results (Azeez & Priyadarshini, 2018)[23]. Women in Bangladesh's private sector are the focus of this research, which aims to examine how factors that contribute to the glass ceiling impact work satisfaction and the desire to move jobs. According to the report, women in the banking industry are

more satisfied with their jobs than women in the telecommunications industry. Furthermore, the study discovered that while glass ceiling-related variables have no significant link with women's work happiness, there are some glass ceiling elements that statistically substantially affect women's decisions to change or transfer occupations. Those who believe they are discriminated against by any male coworker, or who believe they are being discriminated against in their attempts to advance to higher levels of management, or who believe they are being discriminated against in promotions, or who believe they have less job security, are more likely to change jobs. To remedy the problem, the business should take a number of steps, including raising awareness, implementing standard and ethical human resource procedures, and enforcing stringent regulations against discriminatory attitudes and conduct (Nazmul, Islam, & Mahmudul Alam, 2016)[50].

The impacts of the glass ceiling syndrome on women's professional progression in the construction business are investigated in this study. Data was collected using a standardized questionnaire that was delivered to employees of several construction businesses. The findings show that some of the hurdles to women's career progression in construction listed in the literature persist in Nigeria, with the exception of gender equality in terms of employment and career growth opportunities. In addition, women's underrepresentation in the Nigerian construction sector begins with course selection and schooling and continues through the recruiting process (Kolade & Kehinde, 2012)[51].

2.3 Summary of major study in glass ceiling on career advancement of women

S.No	Author(s)/ Researcher(s)	Findings
1.	Dimovski, V., Skerlavaj, M., & Man, M. M. K (2010)[52].	limits the advancement of female managers and creates a barrier to women's professional development prospects by demonstrating that women do not get adequate organizational assistance, such as networking, mentorship, and family-friendly programs.
2.	Sposito, S.A.(2013)[6].	The visible and invisible barrier that divides women from the professional and organizational hierarchical

		levels is referred to as the "glass ceiling." Women may be less inclined than similarly competent males to apply for available positions if they fear the glass ceiling phenomena would work against them.
3.	Bombuwela, P. M., & Alwis, A. C., (2013)[53].	Individual, organizational, and cultural factors all have a substantial impact on women's career development, while family factors have an impact on the Glass Ceiling.
4.	Madhulata. (2016)[54].	Organizational factor, personal factor, stereotype factor, socio-cultural element, political factor, and sexual harassment were the most influential factors.
5.	Reddy, P. J. L. (2020)[55].	Cultural factors play a larger impact in preventing women from advancing in their careers, and management observations regarding women achieving higher positions play a big effect.
6.	Thiranagama.,W. (2021)[56].	The so-called "glass ceiling" still exists in many parts of the world. Cooperators, on the other hand, do not believe in the existence of a glass ceiling, They claimed that society developed the notion of the glass ceiling effect. The lack of women in top positions in corporations is often said to be attributable to internal qualities of women workers that hamper their growth rather than a glass ceiling.

2.4 Research Gaps

The majority of research is either qualitative or quantitative, however this study used both. Despite the fact that there have only been a few research on the issue of glass ceilings in Nepal, no studies on glass ceilings in Nepal's public sector have been conducted. The determination of this study is to fill a gap discovered by previous research.

Chapter Three

Research Methodology

3.1 Research Philosophies

Pragmatism Research Philosophies was used for examining and assessing ideas and beliefs in terms of how well they work in practice. This study makes the bold claim that it can unite the scientific method and structuralist orientation of traditional approaches with the naturalistic methods and freewheeling orientation of contemporary ones through the use of pragmatism.

3.2 Research Approach

This study was based on the Deductive follow by inductive approach, the truth of the premises is supposed to guarantee the truth of the conclusion. Deductive approach was implemented to conduct the Glass Ceiling Breaking Model, Inductive approach was employed to discover the major reasons how the class ceiling was formed in Nepalese public sectors of Nepal.

3.3 Research Methods

To offer study participants a voice and ensure that study conclusions are based on their experiences this study adopt mixed methods. Quantitative research uses methodological tools to portray the human experience in alpha-numerical categories, Qualitative research, on the other hand, goes into great detail about the quality or content of the human experience and how it is described and analyzed.

3.4 Research Design

The study was conducted using Descriptive cum Exploratory Research design. In this study descriptive research describes the current scenario of Glass Ceiling, exploratory research explore the relationship between Glass Ceiling on Career Advancement.

3.5 Time Horizons

To investigate the existence or absence of an outcome as well as the presence or absence of an exposure at a certain time, this study was based on Cross sectional.

3.6 Sampling Design

Simple Random Sampling was used to do the study. In this sampling method, every person in the population has exactly the same chance of being chosen.

3.7 Study Area

This research looked at nine different sectors, three of which are the Minister, Department and Agencies of public sectors and the other six are the Industrial, Social, Public Utility, Financial, Trading, and Service sectors of State-owned enterprises.

Figure 3 Study Area

To examine the glass ceiling in Nepalese public sectors the selection of this sector was based on the constitution of Nepal. In public sectors, civil service sectors and state owned organization come under the ownership and control of Nepal Government. In both sectors recruitment and selection process is conducted by public service commission which comes under constitutional bodies of Nepal (Secretariate, 2015) [57].

3.8 Study site Justification

The majority of private organizations in Nepal are family businesses, so getting effective and accurate results for glass ceiling in the workplace is one of the main reasons for choosing this sector for the study. In addition, this sector covers a wide range of respondents, so it may be appropriate to address glass ceiling.

3.9 Sample size and Sample distribution

Required sample size was identified by using the following Formula for questionnaires survey:

$$n = \frac{t^2 \times p(1 - P)}{m^2}$$

Step 1 calculation of basic sample size:

Where,

n = required sample size

t = confidence level at 96% (standard value of 2.05)

p = estimated prevalence of the risk factors within the target population in the study area at 50%

m = margin of error at 5% (standard value of 0.05)

Here, $n = 2.05 * \frac{2.05 (0.5 (1-0.5))}{0.05 * 0.05}$

$$n = \frac{4.2025 * (0.5 (1 - 0.5))}{0.05 * 0.05} = 420$$

Step 2: Adjust for expected non-response to get final sample size:

It is estimated that there is chances of 3.5% non-response or missing data/questionnaires, so 3.5% is added in basic sample size:

Here,

3.5% of 420 = 14.7

So, 420 + 14.7 = 434.7

Final Sample size is = 435

Respondents were selected from the two different sectors of public organization through the simple random sampling method. From these sectors, 435 respondents were taken as a sample study.

The qualitative study was require an additional 10% (approximately 40 individuals) of the 435 sample size, although the ultimate sample size was determined by the saturation of information in the field. When the same information is repeated from the next respondent, the researcher recognizes that the information is saturated and was stop collecting data.

3.10 Source of Data

On both primary and secondary sources, this research was built. Two types of research were established. Several statistical techniques were proposed and used to examine the main and secondary data.

3.11 Data Collection Methods and tools

Methods

To investigate a real-life situation in order to establish ecological validity, access to a diverse group of participant's survey method was used to collection quantitative data. For qualitative data Key Informant Interview methods was used: Before the interview, a question was created and pre-tested. This includes persons to interview, as well as others. Create a list of interview questions that includes both open-ended and closed-ended inquiries, while avoiding leading questions. Before the question was delivered to the respondents, a pilot study was undertaken. Based on the comments from the pilot research, several adjustments were made to the question. The replies was recorded on a tape recorder and reported.

Tools

This study was conducted using data collection tools such as Questionnaire. A collection of questionnaires was created for various target groups, and each selected responder was sent one to capture their thoughts. This contains questions with a wide range of responses, closed-ended questions, and limited responses to specified reactions or on a numeric scale.

To obtain the respondents' qualitative views, a voice recorder was used. Respondents' views were noted on paper and then finalized in readable form before analysis.

3.12 Data Analysis

In this study for Quantitative Analysis, Percentage, Mean, Standard deviation, ANOVA, correlation, CFA, EFA and SEM was used.

Frequency/ Percentage were used to explain the view of respondents towards glass ceiling factors that is Social Factors, Personal Factors, Organizational Factors, Working Environment Factors, and Family Factors. A demographic factor was also explained with the help of frequency and percentage.

Mean/ Standard deviation were used to discover the major reasons that promote the ceiling towards female career.

ANOVA was used to analysis the significant different between Education, Marital Status, Job Position, Living Status, Nature of organization with Career advancement. Similarly, correlation was adapted to analysis the significant relationship between working experience, age with career advancement.

EFA was applied to investigate a measure's internal reliability and determine its factor structure.

CFA was adopted to confirm a group of observed variables' factor structure.

SEM was used to quantify and investigate the connections between latent and observable variables in order to develop the Class ceiling breaking model.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was applied to measure five hypotheses which were directed to explore the significant relationship between Social Factors, Personal Factors, Organizational Factors, Working Environment Factors, and Family Factors with Career advancement.

Thematic Analysis for Qualitative Analysis, the study use Thematic Analysis. Thematic analysis explain the major variable and show the reason behind the connection among dependent and independent variables. The interviews was transcribed and translated. The translation from Nepali to English was done by Google translator and checked for accuracy by researcher. It was coded as per to maintain anonymity and themes was generated.

3.13 Test of Research Instruments

Validity: A number of experts were contact to provide feedback and recommendations on the questionnaire. The questionnaire was amended in light of their ideas.

Reliability: The survey was tested with a group of 40 participants. Similarly, the expert, supervisors, and target population have a dialogue. Base on necessary, changes to the questionnaires was made subsequently.

3.14 Ethical Consideration

The researchers were explaining the objectives of the study to each study participants. Written informed consent was taken from each study participants. The participants were interviewed individually. The data was kept confidential and secured in password protected laptop; participants were allocated a code number and their identity was protected.

3.15 Summary of the Methodology

S.N	Objectives	Data Collection	Analysis
1	Analyze the role of demographic factors on women's career advancement,	Survey, KII/ Questionnaire, Voice recorder	Correlative, ANOVA, t-test Thematic Analysis
2	Perceptions of women employees towards glass ceiling factors	Survey/Questionnaire	Frequency, Percentage
3	Barriers that stop women from career advancing	Survey, KII/ Questionnaire, Voice recorder	Mean, Std. Deviation /Thematic Analysis
4	Effective model to break class ceiling.	Survey/Questionnaire	Structural Equation Modeling
EFA, CFA was used to finalized the SEM, Pearson Correlation was used to test the Hypothesis			

Chapter Four

Data Analysis & Discussion

4.1 Demographic Information

Table 4.1 Demographic Characteristics

Particulars		Frequency	Percent		
2. Education	Bachelor	92	21.1		
	Master	332	76.3		
	M.Phil.	4	0.9		
	PhD	7	1.6		
	Total	435	100		
3. Marital status	Unmarried	51	11.7		
	Married	380	87.4		
	Divorce	4	.9		
	Total	435	100.0		
4. Current job position	Special class	1	0.2		
	First class	25	5.7		
	Second class	108	24.8		
	Third class	301	69.2		
	Total	435	100.0		
5. Living Status	Join Family	209	48.0		
	Single Family	226	52.0		
	Total	435	100.0		
6. Nature of Public Sectors	Ministry	65	14.9		
	Department	106	24.4		
	Agencies	136	31.3		
	Stated Owned Organization	128	29.4		
	Total	435	100.0		
Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
7. Work Experience	435	1.00	35.00	11.7011	7.79270
8. Age	435	23.00	58.00	38.3241	8.00393

Source: Field Survey, 2022

When respondents were asked what level of education they had completed, the results indicated that 21.1 % had completed a bachelor's degree, 76.3 % had completed a master's degree, 0.9 % had completed an MPhil degree, and 1.6 % had completed a PhD degree. When it comes to the marital status of Nepal's public sector women respondents, 11.7 % of respondents appear to be single, 87.4 % appear to be married, and only 0.9 % appear to be divorced. In terms of present job position, study shows that 0.2% of respondents are in the special class, 5.7 % are in the first class, 24.8 %

are in the second class, and 69.2% are in the third class. A question on the respondents' living status asked whether they lived with a joint family or a single family. 48% of respondents reported living with a joint family, and 52% with a single family. Among the total respondents in this study, 14.9% are from the Ministry, 25.4% are from the Department, 31.1% are from Agencies and 29.4% are from State owned corporations.

In Nepal's public sectors, women employed respondents had an average of 11.7 years of work experience, typically 1 year to 35 years. The data reveals that the youngest person is 23 years old and the oldest person is 58 years old, with a mean age of 38.32 years.

4.2 Exploratory Factors Analysis

Exploratory Factor Analysis was used in this study as the first phase to confirm and adjust variables. Consequently, the results of exploratory component analysis were both validated and a smaller number of unimportant factors were eliminated.

4.2.1 KMO and Bartlett's Test

Initially, the researcher used exploratory factor analysis to verify the questionnaire's validity and extract the indexes. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy is a statistic that shows how much of a variable's variation is driven by underlying causes (Li, Huang, & Feng, 2020)[58].

Table 4.2 KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.889
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	8289.730
	df	1326
	Sig.	.000

The displayed value of KMO in the preceding Table is more than 0.889, suggesting the existence of an appropriate sample. The substantial p-value of Bartlett's test ($p = 0.000$) demonstrates the existence of correlation between the variables, distinguishing it from an identity matrix; hence, Exploratory Factor Analysis can be done effectively on the current dataset.

4.2.2 Community

Community refers to the percentage of variation that can be explained by a set of characteristics that are common to all of the other observed variables. The degree of

communality may be used to determine whether or not a given element should be kept (Alavi M. , Visentin, Thapa, Hunt, Watson, & Cleary, 2020)[59]. After extraction, communalities should be bigger than 0.30; otherwise, they might cause problems when loading on a specific component. 18 items deleted during the initial EFA and 27 items during extraction EFA, the table shows the communalities of all the items in the data set.

Table 4.3 Communalities

Communalities					
	Initial	Extraction		Initial	Extraction
SF8	.407	.252	OF34	.512	.436
SF9	.386	.225	OF35	.508	.481
SF10	.431	.384	OF36	.435	.376
SF11	.468	.443	FF37	.453	.392
SF12	.615	.679	FF38	.493	.458
SF13	.529	.530	FF39	.397	.339
SF14	.364	.278	FF40	.370	.240
PF15	.289	.175	FF41	.224	.113
PF16	.329	.147	FF42	.359	.355
PF17	.424	.336	FF43	.308	.101
PF18	.458	.456	FF44	.463	.470
PF19	.515	.617	FF45	.313	.090
PF20	.398	.341	CF46	.134	.024
PF21	.503	.485	CF47	.452	.352
PF22	.262	.120	CF48	.414	.266
WE23	.301	.207	CF49	.412	.237
WE24	.452	.413	CF50	.511	.440
WE25	.555	.561	CF51	.317	.185
WE26	.567	.612	CA52	.568	.556
WE27	.358	.224	CA53	.582	.597
WE28	.585	.571	CA54	.439	.438
OF29	.469	.382	CA55	.281	.182
OF30	.526	.436	CA56	.256	.144
OF31	.522	.424	CA57	.456	.446
OF32	.482	.407	CA58	.592	.543
OF33	.458	.417	CA59	.574	.438
Extraction Method: Maximum Likelihood.					

Source: Field Survey, 2022

As seen in the above table, all items save for one have communalities that are more than 0.30, except for the item F8, SF9, SF10, SF14, PF15, PF16, PF17, PF20, PF22, WE23, WE27, OF29, OF36, FF37, FF39, FF40, FF41, FF42, FF43, FF45, CF46, CF47, CF48, CF49, CF51, CA55, CA56.

4.2.3 Total Variance Explained

Total variance findings below, which show the number of components with eigenvalues larger than 1 that should be kept for the Varimax rotation stage of validation.

Table 4.4 Total Variance Explained

Factor	Total Variance Explained								
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	11.003	21.160	21.160	10.406	20.012	20.012	3.735	7.182	7.182
2	3.603	6.929	28.089	2.992	5.754	25.766	3.533	6.794	13.977
3	2.403	4.620	32.709	1.742	3.350	29.116	3.155	6.068	20.044
4	1.993	3.832	36.541	1.390	2.673	31.789	3.130	6.019	26.063
5	1.913	3.679	40.220	1.282	2.465	34.254	2.664	5.123	31.186
6	1.594	3.066	43.286	1.012	1.946	36.200	2.607	5.014	36.200
7	1.526	2.935	46.221						
.....									
52	.216	.416	100.000						

Extraction Method: Maximum Likelihood.
Source: Field Survey, 2022

Total variance explained is also a method of reducing a large number of items into a manageable amount before further investigation (Hoque, Siddiqui, Awang, & Baharu, 2018)[60]. Considering Table, it can be seen that EFA has extracted Factors or dimensions from the EO construct with eigenvalue 11.003 for Factor number 1, 3.603

for Factor number 2, 2.403 for Factor number 3, 1.993 for Factor number 4, 1.913 for factor number 5 and 1.594 for factor number 6, respectively.

4.2.4 Factors Matrix

The data were initially evaluated using exploratory component analysis, a method often used for data reduction and summary. When there are numerous variables in a research survey, the majority of them may be associated, and factor analysis brings the number of factors down to a reasonable level for interpretation.

Table 4.5 Factors Matrix

	Factor Matrix ^a						Factor Matrixa						
	Factor						Factors						
	1	2	3	4	5	6		1	2	3	4	5	6
SF8							OF34	.584					
SF9							OF35	.571					
SF10							OF36	.541					
SF11	.539						FF37						
SF12	.641						FF38						
SF13	.574						FF39						
SF14							FF40						
PF15							FF41						
PF16							FF42						
PF17		.517					FF43						
PF18		.639					FF44						
PF19		.684					FF45						
PF20		.542					CF46						
PF21		.647					CF47	.569					
PF22							CF48						
WE23							CF49						
WE24	.586						CF50	.653					
WE25	.616						CF51						
WE26	.612						CA52	.615					
WE27							CA53	.553					
WE28	.705						CA54						
OF29	.583						CA55						
OF30	.631						CA56						
OF31	.621						CA57	.551					
OF32	.521						CA58	.666					
OF33	.511						CA59	.620					
Extraction Method: Maximum Likelihood.													
a. 6 factors extracted. 5 iterations required.													

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Using Varimax Rotation, Principal Component Analysis first separated 42 variables into 6 categories. Negative factor loadings, cross loadings, and variables with factor loadings of less than 0.3 were eliminated (Costello & Osborne, 2005)[61]. As the greatest likelihood method is used by CFA to extract variables.

4.2.5 Goodness of fit test

Goodness-of-fit is measured by a number of model fit indicators, that look at how well the observed data match up with the theoretical data that the model would predict (Alavi M. , Visentin, Thapa, Hunt, Watson, & Cleary, 2020)[59]. Model fit indices can be used with whether thresholds or hypothesis testing to decide if the proposed model should be thrown out or kept. In CFA, a key step is figuring out how well the proposed model fits the observed data. This is called the "goodness of fit," and it is related to how well the model accounts for covariance.

Table 4.6 Goodness of fit test

Goodness-of-fit Test		
Chi-Square	df	Sig.
1984.168	1029	.000

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The goodness of the fit test was conducted with the help of chi-square. The result shows that ($\chi^2=1984.168$, $df=1029$) was significant at $p=0.000$. Which indicates that the model is fit.

4.2.6 Rotated Factors Matrix

Researcher intended to analyze the Rotation matrix. There were a total of 25 statements that had a considerable impact on the six variables. It is advised to eliminate any items with loadings of less than 0.4 and for all factor loadings to be more than 0.5 (Maskey, Fei, & Nguyen, 2018)[62]. Because of this, all factor loadings were analyzed. The Factors and their item loadings are shown in the table, together with the variation explained by each one of them.

Table 4.7 Rotated Factors Matrix and Reliability of factors

Rotated Factor Matrix ^a							Cronbach's alpha
	Factor						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
Social Factors							0.788
SF10				.515			
SF11				.562			

SF12				.739			
SF13				.655			
Personal Factors							0.776
PF17					.552		
PF18					.659		
PF19					.782		
PF20					.571		
PF21					.658		
Working Environment Factors							0.812
WE24		.513					
WE25		.662					
WE26		.725					
WE28		.597					
Organizational Factors							0.730
OF32			.549				
OF33			.555				
OF35			.581				
Family Factors							0.706
FF38						.617	
FF39						.503	
FF42						.581	
FF44						.651	
Career Advancement							0.809
CA52	.625						
CA53	.704						
CA54	.621						
CA57	.595						
CA58	.512						
Extraction Method: Maximum Likelihood. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.							
a. Rotation converged in 8 iterations.							

Source: Field Survey, 2022

In all, there were twenty five elements placed onto the six factors at the conclusion of EFA. Social Factors include four items fit well together; Personal Factors include five items fit well together; working environment factors include four items fit well together; organizational factors include three items fit well together; Family factors include four items fit well together and career advancement consisted five items fit well together.

Furthermore, Cronbach's measure was used to verify the adequacy of each factor and its associated elements (Ahrens, Lirani, & Francisco, 2020)[63]. Cronbach's alpha, whose value must be more than 0.70, is used to determine internal consistency of items (Taber, 2018)[64]. The values of Cronbach's alpha (α) are Social factors 0.788, Personal factors 0.776, working environment factors 0.812, organizational factors, 0.730, family factors 0.706 and career advancement 0.809.

4.2.7 Factor Transformation Matrix

Table 4.8 Factor Transformation Matrix

Factor Transformation Matrix						
Factor	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	.510	.531	.422	.461	.096	.241
2	.049	-.170	-.143	-.116	.884	.392
3	-.624	.023	-.052	.425	-.190	.625
4	.229	-.267	.416	-.549	-.313	.551
5	-.542	.297	.649	-.267	.263	-.237
6	.035	-.728	.452	.470	.079	-.195

Extraction Method: Maximum Likelihood.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Source: Field Survey, 2022

4.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

More reliable factor analysis techniques are used to evaluate whether the measurements of an object are consistent with the researcher's knowledge of its nature. Confirmatory factor analysis is one such technique (Prudon, 2015)[65]. The major goal of CFA was to examine the model's component structure using statistical tests, as well as the link between the variables and their associated items. AMOS 20.0 was used to perform CFA in this investigation (Mishra, 2016)[66].

4.3.1 CFA Model

In addition, other criteria for assessment demonstrate that the model is an adequate match for the data. In the case of standard regression weights, every single one of them was higher than .5. The conclusion demonstrated that the model was suitable for the information available, and as a consequence, no additional enhancement or adjustment was required.

Figure 4 Confirmatory Factor Analysis Model

Factor 1, Social Factor: The measure SF11 has a factor loading of 0.69, indicating that when social factors increase by one standard deviation, SF11 increases the standard deviation is .69. The variable SF13 has a factor loading of 0.75, indicating that when the social factor increases by one standard deviation, SF13 increases the standard deviation is 0.75. The variable SF12 has a factor loading of 0.83, indicating that as the Social factor increases by one standard deviation, so does SF12 the standard deviation is 0.83.

Factor 2, Personal Factor: The measure PF20 has a factor loading of 0.61, indicating that when Personal factors increase by one standard deviation, PF20 increases the standard deviation is 0.61. The variable PF18 has a factor loading of 0.66, indicating that when the Personal factor increases by one standard deviation, PF18 increases the standard deviation is 0.66. The variable PF21 has a factor loading of 0.70, indicating that as the Personal factor increases by one standard deviation, so does PF21 the standard deviation is 0.70. The variable PF19 has a factor loading of 0.76, indicating that as the Personal factor increases by one standard deviation, so does PF19 the standard deviation is 0.76.

Factor 3, working environment: The measure WE24 has a factor loading of 0.66, indicating that when working environment increase by one standard deviation, WE24 increases the standard deviation is 0.66. The variable WE26 has a factor loading of 0.70, indicating that when the working environment increases by one standard deviation, WE26 increases the standard deviation is 0.70. The variable WE28 has a factor loading of 0.79, indicating that as the working environment increases by one standard deviation, so does WE28 the standard deviation is 0.79.

Factor 4, Organizational Factor: The measure OF33 has a factor loading of 0.63, indicating that when organizational factors increase by one standard deviation, OF33 increases the standard deviation is 0.63. The variable OF35 has a factor loading of 0.66, indicating that when the organizational factor increases by one standard deviation, OF35 increases the standard deviation is 0.66. The variable OF32 has a factor loading of 0.67, indicating that as the organizational factor increases by one standard deviation, so does OF32 the standard deviation is 0.70. The variable OF29 has a factor loading of 0.67, indicating that as the organizational factor increases by one standard deviation, so does OF29 the standard deviation is 0.67. The variable OF30 has a factor loading of 0.71, indicating that as the organizational factor increases by one standard deviation, so does OF30 the standard deviation is 0.71.

Factor 5, Family Factor: The measure FF38 has a factor loading of 0.70, indicating that when family factor increase by one standard deviation, FF38 increases the standard deviation is 0.70. The variable FF44 has a factor loading of 0.76, indicating that when the family factor increases by one standard deviation, FF44 increases the standard deviation is 0.76.

Factor 6, Career Advancement: The measure CA54 has a factor loading of 0.62, indicating that when career advancement increase by one standard deviation, CA54 increases the standard deviation is 0.62. The variable CA58 has a factor loading of 0.64, indicating that when the career advancement increases by one standard deviation, CA58 increases the standard deviation is 0.64. The variable CA57 has a factor loading of 0.65, indicating that as the career advancement increases by one standard deviation, so does CA57 the standard deviation is 0.65. The variable CA52 has a factor loading of 0.73, indicating that as the career advancement increases by one standard deviation, so does CA52 the standard deviation is 0.73. The variable CA53 has a factor loading of 0.75, indicating that as the career advancement increases by one standard deviation, so does CA53 the standard deviation is 0.75.

4.3.2 CFA Model specification and Results

Goodness of fit indices

AMOS 20 was used to test the model's maximum likelihood (ML) estimate. The table summarizes the outcomes of CFA, which demonstrated that the Chi square value ($\chi^2=420.060$, $df= 194$) was significant at $p 0.000$.

RMR (Root Mean Square Residual) and GFI (Goodness of Fit Index)

Here, the value should be more than 0.9, resulting in $GFI =.918$ and $AGFI =.893$. The result indicates the model's acceptability.

Incremental / Comparative GOF

All five fit indices should be greater than 0.9. The NFI (Normated Fit Index) was.881, RFI (Relative Fit Indices) was.859, IFI (Incremental Fit Index) was.932, TLI (Tucker-Lewis coefficient) was.919, and CFI (Comparative Fit Indices) was.932. The result indicates the model's acceptability.

Parsimony –Adjusted Measures

For a high GOF, all values should be more than.5. $PRATIO=.840$, $PNFI=.740$, and $PCFI=.782$. The result indicates the model's acceptability.

Table 4.9 Model Fit Measures

Measure	Estimate	Threshold (Gaskin & Lim, 2016)	Interpretation
CMIN (Chi-square statistics)	420.060	--	--
DF (Degrees of Freedom)	194	--	--
CMIN/DF	2.165	Between 1 and 3	Excellent
CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	0.932	>0.95	Acceptable
SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Residual)	0.061	<0.08	Excellent
RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation)	0.052	<0.06	Excellent
PClose (p value when RMSEA is > 0)	0.321	>0.05	Excellent

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The results shown in the table imply that the model may be used for future studies. Every metric surpassed the threshold for approval.

4.4 Relationship between Demographic Characteristic and Career Advancement

4.4.1 Work experience and Career Advancement

Table 4.10 Work Experience and Career Advancement

Correlations			
		work experience	Career Advancement
work experience	Pearson Correlation	1	-.026
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.587
	N	435	435
Career Advancement	Pearson Correlation	-.026	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.587	
	N	435	435

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level 2-tailed.

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The relationship between work experience and career advancement was examined using the Pearson correlation test. There was no correlation between work experience and progress in one's career, according to the findings ($r=-.026$, $p=.587$). For every one point of work experience, the R value indicates a-.026-point decline in career advancement, suggesting a negative association between work experience and career progression. It indicates that the when employees remain in same position for more

that stipulated time frame in the policy/ regulation then career advancement doesn't seem to be growth, although she has gain more work experience. This is related with "job enlargement but no job enrichment" form promotional activities. Despite the fact that a person may be eligible for job enrichment after holding the same job position for a considerable amount of time, if she is not promoted to a higher level of employment or if she is not eligible for job enrichment, then it may appear that he or she is not making substantial progress in their career.

4.4.2 Education and Career Advancement

Table 4.11 Education and Career Advancement (ANOVA)

ANOVA						
Career Advancement						
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Between Groups	8.187	3	2.729	3.903	.009	
Within Groups	301.344	431	.699			
Total	309.531	434				
Multiple comparisons						
Dependent Variable: Career Advancement						
LSD						
(I) Education level	(J) Education level	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Bachelor	Master	-.03143	.09852	.750	-.2251	.1622
	M.Phil	.85307*	.42708	.046	.0137	1.6925
	PhD	.84097*	.32784	.011	.1966	1.4853
Master	Bachelor	.03143	.09852	.750	-.1622	.2251
	M.Phil	.88451*	.42059	.036	.0578	1.7112
	PhD	.87240*	.31936	.007	.2447	1.5001
M.Phil	Bachelor	-.85307*	.42708	.046	-1.6925	-.0137
	Master	-.88451*	.42059	.036	-1.7112	-.0578
	PhD	-.01211	.52410	.982	-1.0422	1.0180
PhD	Bachelor	-.84097*	.32784	.011	-1.4853	-.1966
	Master	-.87240*	.31936	.007	-1.5001	-.2447
	M.Phil	.01211	.52410	.982	-1.0180	1.0422

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table shows a significant difference of education level and career advancement across four education level (F=3.903, df1= 3, p:-value=0.009) at 5% level of significance. It

identify the education have relation with the career advancement. Multiple comparison tests for different education level of employee and their career advancement.

As per this table, Bachelor level of employees education are significantly different from the MPhil and PhD level of employees education where the p values of the test are less than 5%, respectively in that Bachelor level employees education has no significant different from Master, PhD level because the P value is higher than 0.05 level. Meanwhile, Master level education has significant different from MPhil and PhD level employees education but there was no significant different between master level employees education from bachelor level employees education as p-value is more than 5%. Similarly, MPhil level employees education is significantly different from the Bachelor and Master level employees education as the p-value are less than 5%, in that MPhil is not significantly different from PhD level of employees as the p-value is more that 5%. But PhD level employees education has significant different from Bachelor and master level of employees education, whereas PhD has no significant different from MPhil level of employees education as P-value is less and more than 5%. Therefore Education level of employee has relationship with career advancement. Higher level of education aids in career advancement through internal and external sources of recruitment and selection as prescribed by law, regulation, and statute. Through internal sources, if an employee has a master's or PhD, she is eligible for promotion based on performance evaluation and working efficiency, with internal competition taking into account the additional marks from the aforementioned educational levels. However, she will be qualified for the open competition in the second and first class gazette level or the 8th, 9th, and 10th level corporation opens via the external body competition in the designated vacant seat through the external source of recruitment and selection.

4.4.3 Marital Status and Career Advancement

Table 4.12 Marital Status and Career Advancement (ANOVA)

ANOVA					
Career Advancement					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.657	2	.329	.460	.632

Within Groups		308.874	432	.715		
Total		309.531	434			
Multiple comparisons						
Dependent Variable: Career Advancement LSD						
(I) Marital Status	(J) Marital Status	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Unmarried	Married	.12085	.12610	.338	-.1270	.3687
	Divorce	.11780	.43905	.789	-.7451	.9807
Married	Unmarried	-.12085	.12610	.338	-.3687	.1270
	Divorce	-.00305	.42500	.994	-.8384	.8323
Divorce	Unmarried	-.11780	.43905	.789	-.9807	.7451
	Married	.00305	.42500	.994	-.8323	.8384
*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.						

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table shows that an analysis of career advancement and marital status shows no significant difference ($F=0.460$, $df_1=2$, $p\text{-value}=0.632$) at 5% level of significance. Relationship between career advancement and marital status does not exist. The table above shows that the p-values for the test of different marital status of employees and their career advancement show that among unmarried employees, there is no difference between them and married or divorced employees, where the p-values for the test are greater than 5%. Similarly, married employees are no different from unmarried or divorced employees. There are no differences between employees who are divorced and those who are married or unmarried since the P-value is over 5%. The findings are supported by qualitative data as well, which indicate that regardless of whether or not they are married, women are required to participate in household activities rather than giving time to planning and implementing their career. This condition does not differ between married and unmarried circumstances.

4.4.4 Job Position Level and Career Advancement (ANOVA)

Table 4.13 Job Position Level and Career Advancement (ANOVA)

Job position level		
	Frequency	Percent
Special class	1	.2
First class	25	5.7
Second class	108	24.8
Third class	301	69.2
Total	435	100.0

ANOVA					
Career Advancement					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	7.872	3	2.624	3.749	.011
Within Groups	301.659	431	.700		
Total	309.531	434			

Source: Field Survey, 2022

As shown in the table ($F=3.749$, $df_1=3$; p -value=0.11) at the 5% level of significance, there is a significant difference in the p value for job position level and employee career advancement between the two groups. It identifies the level of a job position have significant relationship with employee's career advancement within the public sectors. There is a problem with the multiple comparison technique because there is only one number in a specific class.

4.4.5 Living Status and Career Advancement

Table 4.14 Living Status and Career advancement

Group Statistics										
	Family types	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean					
Career Advancement	Join Family	209	3.1252	.82634	.05716					
	Single Family	226	3.0912	.86249	.05737					
Independent samples test										
		Levene's test for equality of variances		t-test for equality of means						
		F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. 2-tailed	Mean. Difference	Standard Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Career Advancement	Equal variances assumed	1.077	.300	.420	433	.675	.03405	.08112	.12539	.19349
	Equal variances not assumed			.420	432.453	.674	.03405	.08099	.12512	.19323

Source: Field Survey, 2022

As shown in the table, Levene's test for equality of variances is not statistically significant because the p-value is 379, which confirms that the row of 'Equal variances are assumed', so the study has taken the significant value of the t-test of the same row. Joint and single family employee career advancement rates are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance ($t = -0.420$, $df = 433$; $p\text{-value} = 0.675$). This indicates that family status has no bearing on career advancement. Socially, culturally women have to focus towards house hold activities where as she live in single or in joint family.

4.4.6 Age and Career Advancement

The relationship between Age and career advancement were calculated by means of the Pearson correlation test. Age and career advancement had a no significant relationship ($r = -.084$, $p = .079$), according to the findings. The R value displays the negative relations between the age and career advancement which indicates if there is one point variation in age then it will negatively change in employee career advancement by .079 points.

Table 4.15 Age and Career Advancement (correlation)

Correlations			
		Age	Career Advancement
Age	Pearson Correlation	1	-.084
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.079
	N	435	435
Career Advancement	Pearson Correlation	-.084	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.079	
	N	435	435

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level 2-tailed.

Source: Field Survey, 2022

From the finding it can assume that with the lower in age, employee wants have higher career advancement. Employees who are lower in age want quick upgrade, upward in their career.

4.4.7 Nature of Organization and Career advancement

Table 4.16 Nature of Organization and Career Advancement (ANOVA)

ANOVA						
Career Advancement						
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Between Groups	2.241	3	.747	1.048	.371	
Within Groups	307.289	431	.713			
Total	309.531	434				
Multiple comparisons						
Dependent Variable: Career Advancement						
LSD						
(I) Nature of Organization	(J) Nature of Organization	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Ministry	Department	.16684	.13302	.210	-.0946	.4283
	Agencies	.15730	.12732	.217	-.0929	.4076
	Stated Owned Organization	.22710	.12860	.078	-.0257	.4799
Department	Ministry	-.16684	.13302	.210	-.4283	.0946
	Agencies	-.00953	.10940	.931	-.2246	.2055
	Stated Owned Organization	.06026	.11089	.587	-.1577	.2782
Agencies	Ministry	-.15730	.12732	.217	-.4076	.0929
	Department	.00953	.10940	.931	-.2055	.2246
	Stated Owned Organization	.06979	.10398	.502	-.1346	.2742
Stated Owned Organization	Ministry	-.22710	.12860	.078	-.4799	.0257
	Department	-.06026	.11089	.587	-.2782	.1577
	Agencies	-.06979	.10398	.502	-.2742	.1346
*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.						

Source: Field Survey, 2022

At the 5% level of significance, there is no significant difference in mean values for nature of organization and career advancement across groups ($F=1.048$, $df_1= 3$, $p\text{-value}=0.371$). It determines the nature of the organization have no significant relationship with employee advancement. Multiple comparison tests for different nature of organization and career advancement. As per this table, Ministry level employees are no significantly different from Department, agencies and stated owned organization where the p values of the test are more than 5%, respectively in that Department level employees has no significant different from Ministry, agencies and Stated owned organization because the P value is higher than 0.05 level. Meanwhile, Agencies has no significant different from Ministry, Department and Stated owned organization is not significantly different from Ministry, Department and Agencies as the p- value is more that 5%. Therefore Nature of organization has no with career advancement. This is because, all sectors has their fixed rules and regulation that is directly govern by executive/ recruit and select the employee by autonomous body of the country.

4.5 Demographic barriers on career Advancement

The study had discussed about the gender/ age/ education/ position/ marital status related artificial barriers that interviewee face. During the course of the research, an employee with ten years of experience and forty years of age who works for the Ministry of Finance expressed her opinion that she has encountered artificial barriers due to the fact that she is a woman. She said that she had to get married earlier than her elder brother, where she did not get a supportive environment for her studies, and where she was restricted from going to college on a regular basis, which lowered the quality of her education. She also said that "there is nobody for her to motive to get in her job.

An employee with 10 years of experience having age of 32 who represents the department that investigates money laundering expressed her opinion that there is a close relationship between marital status and gender. As she belong woman, she feels obligated to devote more time to her family, caring for her children and satisfying the demands of her husband and parents, which hinders her ability to advance in her career because she is unable to devote time to her job upgrading. Young female employee from the department of mines and geology, age 29, had a similar viewpoint.

The 48-year-old female officer who works in the Ministry of Law, Justice, and Parliamentary Affairs expresses her opinion that it is normal for women to give birth, breastfeed, raise children through their formative years, and deal with physical weakness during pregnancy due to this natural and biological base of women. However, society believes that women should spend more time at home, which hinders their ability to advance in their careers.

The opinions of thirty-four years old offices from citizen investment trust are in agreement with her that ' "I am a woman who maintains a healthy balance between my job at the office and my responsibilities at home. In addition to the chores I have around the home, I spend the whole day working at my workplace. There are some male members in my family who choose to remain at home all day and do not engage in any kind of employment. They adhere to the ideology that women are better suited to performing domestic responsibilities. This, in my opinion, is the creation of gender-based artificial barriers "'.

New and young officer from the Ministry of Health and Population shared her viewpoint that as I am in the beginning years of my service career, I ask for the challenge job that will enrich my career path, but my senior male office positively inhibits me by saying, "you are quit young now you have lot of years to cover such types of job in the future so please give this opportunities to another person." I am unable to compel him since I am a new employee; such sorts of impediments not only prevent young employees from making progress in their careers but also demotivate them to do job.

A senior nurse in charge of Bir Hospital's nursing department shared her opinion that there is a lot of competition among women in the field, and that this competition is unhealthy because women themselves pull the other women's feet down. "One senior nursing madam collapse here higher position when she got retired," she said. "Women enemy were women."

In conclusion, following are the point that stops women in their career advancement

Marital Statue

Women have a greater sense of freedom and autonomy before they get married, but after they do, they have to devote more time to the responsibilities of running the household.

Gender

Women are expected, both socially and culturally, to successfully juggle the demands of their families and careers in the workplace simultaneously.

Mother's primary responsibility is to care for her infant child; she will have fewer opportunities for movement until she is no longer required to participate in child care activities.

Age

Younger workers are discouraged from taking advantage of opportunities by higher-level officers.

There is an age limit imposed by government policy (No policy to apply for job vacancy above 35 years)

Position

The higher-level office makes every effort to prevent junior level workers from obtaining top positions especially in Nursing.

4.6 Perceptions towards glass ceiling factors

4.6.1 Social Factor

Table 4.17 Perception towards social factors in relation to career advancement

S.N	Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
SF11	Women's performance in the workplace is regarded as inadequate.	60	169	90	97	19	435
		13.8%	38.9%	20.7%	22.3%	4.4%	100%
SF12	In our society, women are viewed as unsuitable for higher-level positions.	80	152	73	109	21	435
		18.4%	34.9%	16.8%	25.1%	4.8%	100%
SF13	In our society, women are regarded to be less committed at workplace.	52	156	81	106	40	435
		12.0%	35.9%	18.6%	24.4%	9.2%	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2022

"Women's performance in the workplace is considered as inadequate," was the first statement under Social Factors. The majority of workers agreed with this statement (38.9%), and 13.8% strongly agreed. Only 22.3% of employees disagreed with the statement, 4.4% strongly disagreed, in total 26.7% employees disagreed with the statement. Similarly, 20.7% of workers were unsure, indicating neutral satisfaction with the statement. The majority of workers (52.7%) agreed with the aforementioned statement overall.

The second statement, which was related to the social factor, "In our society, women are considered as unsuited for higher-level positions." The majority of employees (34.9 percent) agreed and (18.4%) respondents to a survey said that they agreed with this statement. However, 25.1% of employees disagreed with this assertion, and 4.8% of them severely disagreed. In a similar vein, 16.8% of workers expressed neutral satisfaction with this claim. The majority of workers (53.3 percent) concurred with the aforementioned claim. Employee disapproval of this statement was at 29.9%.

The third Social Factor statement is, "In our society, women are perceived to be less devoted at work." Similar to earlier comments, employees members responded positively, saying they agreed (35.9%) and strongly agreed (12%) with this one. Only 24.4% of employees disagreed with the same, and 9.2% strongly disagreed. Employee indifferent pleasure with this statement was demonstrated by 18.6% of them. In total 47.9% of employees said they agreed or strongly agreed with the aforementioned statement. Only 33.6% of the workforce disagreed with this statement.

4.6.2 Personal Factor

Table 4.18 Perception towards personal factors in relation to career advancement

S.N	Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
PF18	Women are unable to work full-time.	8	27	29	188	183	435
		1.8%	6.2%	6.7%	43.2%	42.1%	100.0
PF19	Women have low self-esteem and lack professional confidence.	4	31	20	164	216	435
		0.9%	7.1%	4.6%	37.7%	49.7%	100.0
PF20	Women are under qualified for certain jobs.	2	39	62	173	159	435
		0.5%	9%	14.3%	39.8%	36.6%	100.0
PF21	Women are reluctant to accept responsibility.	4	14	19	172	226	435
		0.9%	3.2%	4.4%	39.5%	52%	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2022

“Women are unable to work full-time,” was the first statement under Personal Factors. The majority of workers disagreed with this statement (43.2%), and 42.1% strongly disagreed. Only 6.2% of employees agreed with the statement, 1.8% strongly agreed, in total 8% employees agreed with the statement. Similarly, 6.7% of workers were unsure, indicating neutral satisfaction with the statement. The majority of workers (85.3%) disagreed with the aforementioned statement overall.

The second statement, which was related to the personal factor, “Women have low

self-esteem and lack professional confidence." The majority of employees (49.7 percent) strongly disagreed and 37.7% respondents to a survey said that they strongly disagreed with this statement. However, 7.1% of employees agreed with this assertion, and 0.9% of them severely agreed. In a similar vein, 4.6% of workers expressed neutral satisfaction with this claim. The majority of workers (87.4 percent) disapprove with the statement. Employee approved of this statement was at 8%.

The third Personal Factor statement is, "Women are under qualified for certain jobs." Similar to earlier comments, employees members responded positively, saying they disagreed (39.8%) and strongly disagreed (36.6%) with this one. Only 9% of employees agreed with the same, and 0.5% strongly disagreed. Employee indifferent pleasure with this statement was demonstrated by 14.3% of them. In total 76.4% of employees said they disagreed or strongly disagreed with the aforementioned statement. Only 9.5% of the workforce agreed with this statement.

The last line in the Personal Factor, "Women are reluctant to accept responsibility." Most workers gave positive feedback, saying that they strongly disagreed (52%) and disagreed (39.5%) with this statement. Only 4.1 percent of employees responded negatively, with 3.2 percent agreeing and 0.9 percent strongly agreeing with the same. Similar to that, 4.4 percent of the workforce responded with a response that indicated neutral pleasure with the assertion. The majority of workers, or 91.5 percent, disagreed with the aforementioned claim.

4.6.3 Working Environment

Table 4.19 Perception towards working environment in relation to career advancement

S.N	Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
WE24	Women's Competitiveness with male is regards as a negative trait.	47	166	65	122	35	435
		10.8%	38.2%	14.9%	28.0%	8%	100.0
WE26	When women hold senior positions, male employees feel uneasy to work.	80	170	83	84	18	435
		18.4%	39.1%	19.1%	19.3%	4.1%	100.0
WE28	If women ready to handle higher position she has to face Isolation at work.	63	158	94	106	14	435
		14.5%	36.3%	21.6%	24.4%	3.2%	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2022

“Women’s Competitiveness with male is regards as a negative trait," was the first statement under Working Environment Factors. The majority of workers agreed with this statement (38.2%), and 10.8% strongly agreed. Only 28% of employees disagreed with the statement, 8% strongly disagreed, in total 36% employees disagreed with the statement. Similarly, 14.9% of workers were unsure, indicating neutral satisfaction with the statement. The majority of workers (49%) agreed with the aforementioned statement overall.

The second statement, which was related to the Working Environment factor, “When women hold senior positions, male employees feel uneasy to work." The majority of employees (39.1 percent) agreed and the strongly agreed (18.4%) respondents to a survey said that they agreed with this statement. However, 19.3% of employees disagreed with this assertion, and 4.1% of them severely disagreed. In a similar vein, 19.1% of workers expressed neutral satisfaction with this claim. The majority of workers (57.5 percent) concurred with the aforementioned claim. Employee disapproval of this statement was at 23.4%.

The third Working Environment Factor statement is, “If women ready to handle higher position she has to face Isolation at work." Similar to earlier comments, employees members responded positively, saying they agreed (36.3%) and strongly agreed (14.5%) with this one. Only 24.4% of employees disagreed with the same, and 3.2% strongly disagreed. Employee indifferent pleasure with this statement was demonstrated by 21.6% of them. In total 50.8% of employees said they agreed or strongly agreed with the aforementioned statement. Only 27.6% of the workforce disagreed with this statement.

4.6.4 Organizational Factors

Table 4.20 Perception towards organizational factors in relation to career advancement

S.N	Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
OF29	Women's progress and gender equality are not prioritized by organization.	42	162	95	126	10	435
		9.7%	37.2%	21.8%	29%	2.3%	100.0
OF30	Women receive fewer opportunities for professional development at work.	49	214	82	79	11	435
		11.3%	49.2%	18.9%	18.2%	2.5%	100.0
OF32	Organizational policies that encourage women's professional	97	217	56	55	10	435
		22.3%	49.9%	12.9%	12.6%	2.3%	100.0

	advancement are lacking.						
OF33	Women are underrepresented in the policy making process.	128	240	34	28	5	435
		29.4%	55.2%	7.8%	6.4%	1.1%	100.0
OF35	Women face a lack of mentorship and managerial training at work place.	64	204	86	73	8	435
		14.7%	46.9%	19.8%	16.8%	1.8%	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2022

“Women's progress and gender equality are not prioritized by organization,” was the first statement under organizational Factors. The majority of workers agreed with this statement (37.2%), and 9.7% strongly agreed. 29% of employees disagreed with the statement, 2.3% strongly disagreed, in total 31.3% employees disagreed with the statement. Similarly, 21.8% of workers were unsure, indicating neutral satisfaction with the statement. The majority of workers (46.9%) agreed with the aforementioned statement overall.

The second statement, which was related to the Organizational factor, “Women receive fewer opportunities for professional development at work.” The majority of employees (49.2 percent) agreed and 11.3% respondents to a survey said that they strongly agreed with this statement. However, 18.2% of employees disagreed with this assertion, and 2.5% of them severely disagreed. In a similar vein, 18.9% of workers expressed neutral satisfaction with this claim. The majority of workers (60.5 percent) approved with the statement. Employee disapproved of this statement was at 20.7%.

The third Organizational Factor statement is, “Organizational policies that encourage women's professional advancement are lacking.” Similar to earlier comments, employees members responded positively, saying they agreed (49.9%) and strongly agreed (22.3%) with this one. Only 12.6% of employees disagreed with the same, and 2.3% strongly disagreed. Employee indifferent pleasure with this statement was demonstrated by 12.9% of them. In total 72.2% of employees said they agreed or strongly agreed with the aforementioned statement. Only 9.5% of the workforce disagreed with this statement.

The fourth line in the Organizational Factor, “Women are underrepresented in the policy making process.” Most workers gave negative feedback, saying that they agreed (55.2%) and strongly agreed (29.4%) with this statement. Only 4.1 percent of employees responded positively, with 6.4 percent disagreeing and 1.4 percent strongly

disagreeing with the same. Similar to that, 7.8 percent of the workforce responded with a response that indicated neutral pleasure with the assertion. The majority of workers, or 84.6 percent, agreed with the aforementioned claim.

The last line in the Organizational Factor, “Women face a lack of mentorship and managerial training at work place.” Most workers gave negative feedback, saying that they agreed (46.9%) and strongly agreed (29.4%) with this statement. Only 16.8 percent of employees responded positively, with 1.8 percent disagreeing and 1.4 percent strongly disagreeing with the same. Similar to that, 19.8 percent of the workforce responded with a response that indicated neutral pleasure with the assertion. The majority of workers, or 76.3 percent, agreed with the aforementioned claim.

4.6.5 Family Factor

Table 4.21 Perception towards family factor in relation to career advancement

S.N	Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
FF38	Taking care of my family is a hindrance to my career growth.	12	94	63	160	106	435
		2.8%	21.6%	14.5%	36.8%	24.4%	100.0
FF44	My dedication to family life is a hindrance to my professional advancement.	16	69	81	195	74	435
		3.7%	15.9%	18.6%	44.8%	17%	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The first statement, related to the Family factor, “Taking care of my family is a hindrance to my career growth.” The majority of employees (36.8 percent) disagreed and 24.4% respondents to a survey said that they strongly disagreed with this statement. However, 21.6% of employees agreed with this assertion, and 2.8% of them severely agreed. In a similar vein, 14.5% of workers expressed neutral satisfaction with this claim. The majority of workers (61.2 percent) disapproved with the statement. Employee approved of this statement was at 24.4%.

The second Family Factor statement is, “My dedication to family life is a hindrance to my professional advancement.” Similar to earlier comments, employees members responded positively, saying they disagreed (44.8%) and strongly disagreed (17%) with this one. Only 15.9% of employees agreed with the same, and 3.7% strongly agreed. Employee indifferent pleasure with this statement was demonstrated by 18.6% of them. In total 61.8% of employees said they agreed or strongly agreed with the

aforementioned statement. Only 19.6% of the workforce disagreed with this statement.

4.7 Barriers to Career Advancement

Figure 5 Barriers to Career Advancement

Researchers assess the main barriers to women's job advancement in Nepal's public sector. Every factor is measured using a five-liker scale. Since 2.5 is the midpoint for the viewpoint, 1 indicates strong agreement, 5 indicates extreme disagreement; similarly, all questions are posed in the opposite manner. The findings indicate that organizational issues are the primary barriers that prevent women from advancing in their careers, as shown by the mean value of 2.29, which is lower than 2.5. In a similar vein, the social factor is yet another barrier that prevents women from advancing in their careers, and its mean value is 2.36. The other elements, which include family, personal, and working environments, do not prevent women from advancing their careers in the Nepalese public sectors, where the mean values for each category are 2.90, 2.71, and 2.59 correspondingly.

4.8 Major problems in advancing higher hierarchy roles

The study had discussed about the major problems face by female officer in advancing higher hierarchy roles. During the course of the study, a 31-year-old officer from the Department of Cooperative stated that the management committee has difficulty accepting women's work performance and leadership positions because they

continue to believe that women are unable to complete the assigned task in an appropriate manner and have higher family responsibilities. However, women face such kinds of barriers she wants to upgrade and step on. A 33-year-old Agriculture Development Bank Ltd. officer who shared a similar perspective stated that she believed that the male-dominated society, cultural and traditional views of women as inferior, the obligation to support one's family, and workplace harassment prevent women from advancing in their careers.

Another official, this one 43 years old and working for the Agriculture Development Bank, voiced her opinion as follows: "Most notably, women are not offered chances similarly to males." When they accomplish something novel, members of society comment that the "stereotype" is broken. The government organizations have a "Mahila Quota" for the women. I believe that the quotas should be removed as well, and both men and women should be treated equally to everything. Quotas make women appear feebler, and people also think that they were recruited based on quota, so people believe that they were recruited because of quotas.

Forty two years old female officer from survey department list the point that she face during work in relation to career advancement:

- Lack of Knowledge Sharing(less participation of women)
- No sharing/listening/communicating importance issue
- Political environment (nepotism favoritism)
- No security and safety

Forty five years old office from Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock put her view in points that are given below:

Time management issues

- No circle of trustee as their male counterpart
- Issue of crisis management
- Women are more vulnerable to being manipulated at work because of their inherent nature of empathy/trustfulness.
- Prioritization of work
- Rising boys right since their formative years
- Unable to give full time at work
- Unable to fit physically regularly
- Reluctant mentality of subordinates to work under leadership of women

"Women have to face problems from home to office regularly even if they work in a smart manner," says an Experienced 50 year's old female officer from the rural health institute, Doramba sailing Ga. Pa Tokarpur. Some of their male friends even hide the work related files; some of them even pen the required documents. Some of their male friends even express that 'you got a job as a female, why do you need a promotion? "Just do a simple job and take care of your family. "Women who work in rural areas have more problems than those who work in urban areas." she say ; I have to travel by foot from one place to another, so to complete the task, I face obstacles like lack of physical infrastructure like roads, electricity, and a weak communication network. I face obstacles to completing my job at a given time.

A female officer from the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology expressed her frustration that women still do not have the same educational opportunities as men. Even if some women manage to receive an education, it won't be as per their needs and wants. In Nepal, barely 5/6 percent of women get the same opportunities as men. Those who have to work and obtain an education outside the house still have a possibility of thinking with a pessimistic attitude, and even if there is no error, men may still attempt to make a riddle, pull their feet, or misbehave, all of which may put an end to an employee's career.

4.9 Structural Equation Modeling

After CFA this section offers the final structural model evaluation. Latent variables that remained after applying CFA were then used to advance SEM (Structure Equation Modeling). The researcher must evaluate a set of regression equations with the help of SEM, which is an extension of GLM (General Linear Model). A popular multivariate method for examining the direct and indirect effects of interactions between observable and latent variables is structural equation modeling (SEM). A variable that has been directly measured and adds to the make-up of a latent variable is referred to as an observed variable in SEM (Ampofo & Aidoo, 2022)[67].

4.9.1 SEM of the study

Figures show a model for breaking the glass ceiling in Nepal's public sectors. Whereas career advancement appears to be a dependent variable on family factors and the work environment, and where the working environment is dependent on three aspects—personal, social, and organizational—in this connection, the glass ceiling can be broken.

Figure 6 Structural Equation Model of the Study

Three variables personal, social and organizational are correlated to each other, if there is improvement in personal factors of women employee that mean “work full-time, develop self-esteem and professional confident, train in organizational required manner, accept given task” by hook or cook. Plus, change in societal thinking pattern that means “belief women performance, viewed positively women for the higher position, trust their work related commitment” in order to lift them in higher position. In addition betterment in organizational factors that is “prioritizes women progress and gender equality, provides opportunities, develop strong career advancement policies, participate women in policy making process”. Change in this three factors create favorable working environment that means “competitiveness with male will regards as positive trait, avoid the feel of uneasy to work with senior women boss, women don’t have to face isolation at work when she is in higher position.

This situation can create career advancement. However family factors will also influence career advancement. If management of taking care of family member is balance then women career advancement will be higher, this will generate plenty of opportunity to progress to top higher position, create equal opportunity to both male and female for career advancement, organizational function will be open to women

for higher level administrative, encouragement to apply women for higher level position will increase and men network will facilitate women in path to career advancement. In this way glass ceiling will be break.

4.9.2 SEM Model specification and Results

Goodness of fit Indices

SEM was used on a model with six components. Figure depicts the proposed measuring model. The measurement was assessed using AMOS 20's maximum likelihood (ML) estimate. Results of the final SEM are given in the table. The outcome revealed that the Chi square statistic ($\chi^2 = 475.275$ df= 200) was significant at $p < 0.000$, suggesting that the data and model suited each other well. CMIN/DF number should be 3 for high fit; however in this case, CMIN/DF is 2.376. As a result, no further approaches are required for assessment.

Incremental / Comparative GOF

All five fit indices should be greater than 0.9. The NFI (Normated Fit Index) was .899, RFI (Relative Fit Indices) was .901, IFI (Incremental Fit Index) was .918, TLI (Tucker-Lewis coefficient) was .904 and CFI (Comparative Fit Indices) was .917. The result indicates the model's acceptability.

Parsimony –Adjusted Measures

For a high GOF, all values should be more than .5. PRATIO=.866, PNFI=.749, and PCFI=.794. The result indicates the model excellent.

RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of approximation)

It shows the Comparative badness of fit Index, which should be .5, implying that while we improve the RMSEA, the track of RMR must also be maintained low. Lower RMSEA values (.06 or less) indicate better model fit. The RMSEA was .056, indicating that no additional improvement was required.

Table 4.22 Goodness of Fit statistics for the Final SEM

Measure	Estimate	Threshold(Gaskin & Lim, 2016)[68].	Interpretation
CMIN(Chi-square statistics)	475.275	--	--
DF(Degrees of Freedom)	200	--	--
CMIN/DF	2.376	Between 1 and 3	Excellent
CFI(Comparative Fit Index)	0.917	>0.95	Acceptable
SRMR(Standardized Root Mean Residual)	0.059	<0.08	Excellent
RMSEA(Root Mean Square	0.056	<0.06	Excellent

Error of Approximation)								
PClose(p value when RMSEAs>0)		0.055	>0.05		Excellent			
	χ^2/DF	GFI		AGFI		PGFI		
Threshold	1 < X 3	≥ 0.90		≥ 0.90		≥ 0.90		
Estimate	2.376	.907		.882		.717		
	Incremental Fit				Measures Parsimony Fit Indices			
	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI	PRATIO	PNFI	PCFI
Threshold	≥ 0.90	≥ 0.90	≥ 0.90	≥ 0.90	≥ 0.90	≥ 0.50	≥ 0.50	≥ 0.50
Estimate	.899	.901	.918	.904	.917	.866	.749	.794

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Another assessment criteria demonstrates that the model adequately fits the data. When using standard regression weights, the majority weight was more than .5. There was no need for any further improvement or modification since the final result confirmed that the model was appropriate for the provided data set(s).

4.9.3 Hypothesis Testing

Table 4.23 Regression Estimates of Latent Measures

Factor		Factor	Regression Weight	S.E.	C.R.	P
Environment	<---	Personal	.087	.068	1.286	.199
Environment	<---	Social	.390	.056	6.932	***
Environment	<---	Organizational	.660	.079	8.305	***
Family	<---	Environment	.323	.070	4.618	***
Career	<---	Environment	.700	.070	9.968	***
Career	<---	Family	.018	.057	.320	.749

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The table results show that the one predicted route between independent and dependent variables was determined to be significant. For case, the hypothesized path between environment and social factor with CR value of 6.932 (>1.96) was statistically significant (p =.000), environment and organizational factor with CR value 8.305 (>1.96) was significant (p =.000), Family and environment factor with CR value 4.618(>1.96) was significant (p=.000) and career and environment factor with CR value 9.968 (>1.96) was significant (p=.000) similarly, Environment and personal factors with CR value 1.286 (>1.96) was no significant(p=0.199), career and family factor with CR value 0.320(<1.96) was no significant (p=0.749)

4.9.4 Validation Test

The values of CR, AVE, MSV, and MarR (H) indicate that the model is appropriate. The AVE value of social 0.474, personal 0.377, and organizational 0.420, which is

extremely close to the 0.5 cutoff; the CR, MSV, and MaxR (H) values are also inside the threshold, indicating that the model is legitimate.

Table 4.24 Measures of the model's fit.

Latent Variables	CR* (>0.7)	AVE* (>0.5)	MSV* (<AVE)	MaxR(H)* (>0.7)	Social	Personal	Organizational
Social	0.774	0.474	0.271	0.821	0.689		
Personal	0.714	0.377	0.003	0.792	0.053	0.614	
Organizational	0.812	0.420	0.271	0.816	0.521***	0.049	0.648

Composite Reliability: CR, AVE (Average Variance Extracted: AVE is used to test Convergent Validity, Maximum Shared Variance: MSV is used to test Discriminant Validity, MaxR(H): Maximal Reliability

4.9.5 Model Fit Test

Table 4.25 Model Fit Test Using Multivariate Regression

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.878 ^a	.770	.769	.38487	.770	481.770	3	431	.000	2.048
a. Predictors: (Constant), Social, Personal, Organizational										
b. Dependent Variable: Environment										

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.633 ^a	.400	.397	.65559	.400	144.085	2	432	.000	1.924
a. Predictors: (Constant), Environment, Family										
b. Dependent Variable: Career										

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The value of R, which stands for simple correlation, is 0.878 according to multivariate regression analysis. R-square shows the percentage of the dependent variable's total variation that can be attributed to Social, Personal and Organizational. The independent variables (Social, Personal and Organizational) account for 77% of the variance in the dependent variable career, according to the R Square, which is 0.77. The adjusted R Square value is 0.769, which indicate that 76 percent of career advancement was influenced by Social, Personal and Organizational factors.

Similarly, the value of R, which stands for simple correlation, is 0.633 according to multivariate regression analysis. R-square shows the percentage of the dependent variable's total variation that can be attributed to Environment and Family. The

independent variable (Environment and Family) account for 40% of variance in dependent variable (career advancement), according to the R Square, which is 0.400. The adjusted R Square value is 0.397, which indicate that 39% of career advancement was influenced by environment and Family factors. A certain amount of endogenous building variation is regarded acceptable when the R2 values are equal to or higher than 0.10 (Hussain, Fangwei, Siddiqi, Ali, & Shabbir, 2018) [69].

4.9.6 ANOVA test

Table 4.26 ANOVA Test between Dependent and Independent variable

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	214.090	3	71.363	481.770	.000 ^b
	Residual	63.843	431	.148		
	Total	277.932	434			
a. Dependent Variable: Environment						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Social, Personal, Organizational						

Source: Field Survey, 2022

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	123.856	2	61.928	144.085	.000 ^b
	Residual	185.674	432	.430		
	Total	309.531	434			
a. Dependent Variable: Career						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Environment, Family						

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The P-value indicates whether or not the model is valid. As we can see, the significance p-value in this instance is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. It means that the researcher's model is accurate and satisfies the needs of the study (Elsawy & Elbadawe, 2022)[70]. The model is important as a result.

4.9.7 Test of Collinearity

A condition is said to be multicollinear when there is an approximately linear connection between two or more independent variables. This might be any number of variables (Chan, et al., 2022)[71].

Table 4.27 Test of Collinearity

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-.189	.128		-1.477	.140		
	Organizational	.856	.042	.659	20.417	.000	.512	1.952
	Personal	.059	.041	.033	1.433	.153	.987	1.014
	Social	.280	.033	.276	8.526	.000	.508	1.968

a. Dependent Variable: Environment

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1.183	.154		7.689	.000		
	Family	.090	.049	.071	1.822	.069	.907	1.102
	Environment	.641	.041	.607	15.519	.000	.907	1.102

a. Dependent Variable: Career

Source: Field Survey, 2022

When examining the multicollinearity of the imputed component scores, Working Environment is used as the dependent variable, while the other constructs (Social, Personal, and Organizational) are used as independent variables. Tolerance and variance inflation factors (VIF) were used to assess multicollinearity. There is a problem with multicollinearity if the VIF exceeds 4.0 or the tolerance is less than 0.2(Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2010)[72].The Table shows that the VIF values are less than 2 and that the tolerance values are more than 0.5.. As a result, multicollinearity is not a concern for these variables.

When examining the multicollinearity of the imputed component scores, Career advancement is used as the dependent variable, while the other constructs (Family and working environment) are used as independent variables. All VIF values are less than 2 and tolerance values are more than 1, as shown in the Table. As a result, multicollinearity is not a concern for these variables.

4.10 How to break Glass Ceiling

Officer of female gender representing the Agricultural Development Bank's shares, "Even if there is some progress being made in the areas of gender equality and quality, there is still a glass ceiling that exists in the context of Nepal. Male family members in educated families often do not pitch in to help with chores around the home. Because of this, it is essential that children be raised in such a manner that they

are never given the opportunity to discover that various occupations are associated with different genders. Therefore, first and foremost, we need to work on improving the situation at home by having the mother/father treat her children more fairly in terms of distributing toys, picking dress, and how they treated the elderly. It will take some time, but the glass ceiling will be significantly broken as a result of this circumstance in the future”.

50-year-old officer from the Ministry of Physical Infrastructure and Transport has a contrasting viewpoint, stating that "women have to confront any challenge by being strong." It is necessary to overlook any social, cultural, or organizational hurdles and just concentrate on one's own goals. It is necessary to strengthen oneself via education, knowledge, and experience. If any women present their position using this method, nobody will create obstacles."

A 37-year-old officer from the Ministry of Communication and Information Technology states that "every citizen needs to be educated so that this can lead to a transformation of mindset, organization or government should prioritize providing child care facilities as well as age care facilities for working parents, and women should be given priority to duty stations in their preferred locations.

4.11 Correlation between Dependent and Independent Variables

Table 4.28 Correlation between dependent and independent variables

		Correlations					
		Soci al	Person al	Environme nt	Organization al	Famil y	Caree r
Social	Pearson Correlation	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)						
	N	435					
Personal	Pearson Correlation	.115	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.016					
	N	435	435				
Environment	Pearson Correlation	.740 ^{**}	.112	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.019				
	N	435	435	435			
Organizational	Pearson Correlation	.698 ^{**}	.071	.854 ^{**}	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.137	.000			

	N	435	435	435	435		
Family	Pearson Correlation	.355*	.339**	.305**	.429**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		
	N	435	435	435	435	435	
Career	Pearson Correlation	.517*	.102	.629**	.833**	.256**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.033	.000	.000	.000	
	N	435	435	435	435	435	435
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).							
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).							

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between societal factors and career advancement.

Career advancement is linked to social factors using a Pearson Product Moment method. Employees and professional progress have a statistically significant link ($r=.517$, $n=435$, $p<.01$) at the 1% level of significance. The significance is modest, but the relationship is substantial. As a result of the considerable connection, hypothesis 1 is rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between the personal factors and employee career advancement.

To calculate the relationship between a personal characteristic and employee advancement, the Pearson Product Moment method was applied. At the 1% level of significance, the data reveal a significant relationship between personal factors and career advancement ($r=.102$, $n=435$, $p.0.33$). The significant is satisfactory, but the relationship is substantial. As a result of the considerable connection, hypothesis 2 is rejected.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between the working environment and employee career advancement.

The relationship between the workplace and employee career advancement was calculated using the Pearson Product Moment method. At the 1% level of significance, the data reveal a significant relationship between staff career advancement and working environment ($r=.629$, $n=435$, $p<.01$). The significant is modest, but the relationship is substantial. As a result of the considerable connection, hypothesis 3 is rejected.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between the organizational factors and employee career advancement.

To calculate the relationship between organizational component and employee career advancement, the Pearson Product Moment method was utilized. At the 1% level of significance, the data reveal a significant relationship between staff career advancement and organizational factors ($r=.833$, $n=435$, $p<.01$). The significant is modest, but the relationship is substantial. As a result of the considerable connection, hypothesis 4 is rejected.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant relationship between the family factors and employee career advancement

To calculate the relationship between family factor and employee career advancement, the Pearson Product Moment method was utilized. At the 1% level of significance, the data reveal a significant relationship between staff career advancement and family factors ($r=.256$, $n=435$, $p<.01$). The significant is satisfactory, but the relationship is substantial. As a result of the considerable connection, hypothesis 5 is rejected.

Chapter Four

Summary Conclusion and Recommendation

This chapter, review the findings and recommendations from the research. The study's findings and interpretations were discussed, along with their implications for future studies. The results and their interpretation were analyzed, and a summary and conclusion were drawn. Recommendations were made for both current and future academics to consider.

5.1 Summary of the Study

Women find it hard to fight injustices on the work and at home. Despite corporate and government laws, there are few female executives. It's important to study women's workplace involvement, professional growth, and organizational initiatives to promote them. Base on this background the objectives of this study were to identify the Glass Ceiling factors affecting women's career development in public sectors of Nepal. This study covers four sectors that is Ministry, Department, Agencies and stated owned organization in public sectors with the sample of 435 managerial women as participants. By applying the mixed methods following result were withdraw. Study was based on three objectives which were display below:

First objective was to investigate the significant different between Demographic and career advancement, a Pearson correlation analysis was carried out. There was not a significant association between the amount of work experience and the amount of career advancement, as shown by the findings ($r=-0.026$, $p=.587$). The results demonstrate a statistically significant difference in mean education level and job progression across four education levels ($F=3.903$, $df1=3$, $p\text{-value}=0.009$) at the 5% level of significance. There is no statistically significant difference between career advancement and marital status ($F=0.460$, $df1=2$, $p\text{-value}=0.632$) at the 5% level of significance. As indicated by the result ($F=3.749$, $df1=3$; $p\text{-value}=0.11$), there is a significant difference between job position level and employee career advancement. Joint and single family employee career advancement rates are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance ($t= -0.420$, $df= 433$; $p\text{-value} = 0.675$). Age and career advancement were unrelated ($r=-.084$, $p=.079$). Nature of organization and career advancement mean values do not vary significantly among groups ($F=1.048$, $df1=3$, $p=0.371$). From interview women express their view towards demographic factors as, Before marriage, women have more independence and autonomy, but

thereafter, they have more domestic obligations, Socially and culturally, women are expected to manage family and job responsibilities, Mother's main task is to care for her newborn kid; she will have fewer options to relocate until child care is no longer essential, Higher-level authorities prevent younger employees from seizing possibilities, Government policy limits age (No policy to apply for job vacancy above 35 years), The higher-level office prevents junior personnel from getting top nursing posts.

Second objective was to assess the perception of employees towards glass ceiling factors. Social Factors' initial statement first: "Women's workplace performance is unsatisfactory." 39% of employees agreed. Second, "In our culture, women are unfit for higher-level employment." 34.9% of workers agreed. Third Social Statement: "Women are viewed as less dedicated at work." Similar to agreeing remarks (34.9%). Women can't work full time "under Personal Factors. The majority of employees disagreed (43.2%), "Women lack self-esteem and professional confidence", Most workers (49.7%) disagreed, "Women are under qualified for certain positions."" Similar to past responses, 39.8% response disagreed, "Women are unwilling to assume responsibility" was last statement here Majority employees said they strongly disagreed (52 percent). First statement under Working Environment Factors: "Women's competitiveness with males is a bad attribute." 38% of workers agreed, 2nd "When women assume top positions, male colleagues feel uncomfortable." Majority workers (39%) agreed, 3rd "If woman ready to manage greater position she must suffer isolation at work." Employees agreed with (36.3 percent). First under organizational Factors: "Women's advancement and gender equality are not emphasized." 37.2% of employees agreed, Second statement, "Fewer possibilities exist for career advancement for women in the workplace. 49.2% agreed, second place "women are given less opportunity at work to further their careers. Third, 49.9% of employees felt that "organizational measures that support women's professional growth are inadequate." Fourth, "Women are underrepresented in the policy making process." Majority employees (55.2%) agreed, final sentence, "Women lack mentors and management training at work." Majority agreed (46.9 percent). The first assertion, related to Family, is "Caring for my family hinders my work success."" Majority workers (36.8%) disagreed, second Family Factor statement: "My devotion to family life hinders my career growth."" Like past remarks, workers disagreed (44.8 percent).

A third objective was to identify the barriers of career advancement. As per the findings, organizational concerns are the principal hurdles that prohibit women from advancing in their professions, with a mean value of 2.29. Another barrier that inhibits women from advancing in their careers is the social element, which has a mean value of 2.36.

A fourth objective was to explore effective model of glass ceiling. Communalities reduce 19 variables out of a total of 51 variables. Six of the factors were eliminated with the assistance of the Rotated Factors Matrix and the CFA.SEM leads to the conclusion that Career Advancement is a dependent variable. In that working environment is dependent on Personal, Social, and Organizational factors, similarly, family factor was dependent on working environment up to a point. According to the findings, better personal, social, and organizational factors lead to a more productive working environment, which may lead to career advancement. However, family factors play a minor role in career advancement.

The relationship between the independent and dependent variables was calculated using the Pearson Product Moment method. At the 1% level of significance, the data reveal a significant relationship between personal factors and career advancement ($r=.102$, $n=435$, $p.0.33$). The significant is satisfactory, but the relationship is substantial. As a result of the considerable connection, the findings show a substantial link between personal variables and career advancement at the 1% level of significance ($r=.102$, $n=435$, $p.0.33$). The significance is adequate, but the association is considerable. As a consequence of the strong link, the findings show a substantial link between staff career advancement and working environment ($r=.629$, $n=435$, $p.01$) at the 1% level of significance. The significance is little, but the link is considerable. As a consequence of the strong link, the findings show a substantial association between staff career advancement and organizational factors at the 1% level of significance ($r=.833$, $n=435$, $p.01$). The significance is little, but the link is considerable. As a consequence of the strong link, The findings show a significant association between staff career advancement and family factors at the 1% level of significance ($r=.256$, $n=435$, $p.01$). The significance is adequate, but the association is considerable, As a consequence of the strong link.

5.2 Conclusion of the Study

This study was based in to four parts, first is to analyze the role of six demographic factors on career advancement, under this two factors job position and education level seem significant different relationship with career advancement. Similarly, work experience, marital status, living status, age and nature of organization has no significant different with career advancement. Second is to examine the perception towards Glass Ceiling were Social Factor: "Women's performance in the workplace is regarded as inadequate" majority respondents Agreed, "In our society women are viewed as unsuitable for higher-level positions" majority respondents agreed, "In our society women are regarded to be less committed at workplace" majority respondents agreed. Personal Factors: "Women are unable to work full-time" majority respondents disagreed, "Women have low self-esteem and lack professional confidence" majority respondents strongly disagreed, "Women are under qualified for certain jobs" majority respondents disagreed, "Women are reluctant to accept responsibility" majority respondents strongly disagreed. Working Environment: "Women's Competitiveness with male is regards as a negative trait" majority respondents agreed, "When women hold senior positions, male employees feel uneasy to work", majority of respondents agreed, "If women ready to handle higher position she has to face Isolation at work" majority respondents agreed. Organizational Factors: "Women's progress and gender equality are not prioritized by organization" majority respondents agreed, "Women receive fewer opportunities for professional development at work" majority respondents agreed, "Organizational policies that encourage women's professional advancement are lacking" majority respondents agreed, "Women are underrepresented in the policy making process" majority respondents agreed, "Women face a lack of mentorship and managerial training at work place" majority respondents agreed. Family Factors: "Taking care of my family is a hindrance to my career growth" majority respondents disagreed; "My dedication to family life is a hindrance to my professional advancement" majority respondents disagreed. Organizational and social factors are barriers in career advancement of managerial women's in public sectors of Nepal. The effective model of glass ceiling was, the better in personal, organizational and social factors lead to quality of working environment which guides towards to career advancement however family factors play some sort of role in working environment towards career advancement. Hypothesis was tested to measure the

relationship between social, personal, working environment, organizational, family factors on career advancement. All hypotheses were rejected.

5.3 Recommendation of the Study

Social

1. To bring the social transformations regarding gender role thinking, Education has the potential to instill ideals such as equality, justice, and mutual respect. Education need to be used as a significant forum for change at both the household and the school level.
2. Promoting the role of women in public sectors by engaging religious leaders, traditional leaders, and local opinion shapers.

Personal

3. Working women should fully participate in an organization's strategy so they may advance professionally and personally.
4. Women should feel confident in their abilities to take on challenging, demanding, or decisive tasks as needed.
5. Women should set concrete goals and ignore the opinions of their peers and society
6. Women should establish a strong social network, good communication skills, and an open mind to change.
7. Women should take assistance of their family; they should place a higher priority on their own skills and talents and build their careers appropriately.

Organization

8. Organizations should make an effort to develop a framework that is supportive of women, taking into account their specific social and family responsibility.
9. Organizations should provide male workers awareness programs to help them embrace women as equals and stop making gender distinctions in the job they undertake.
10. The organization should support female workers by providing daycare facilities, letting them leave early on weekends, offering the same flexible office hours, and letting them work from home.

Family

11. It is important for male family members to realize that the roles that female family members play in the organization are equivalent to the roles that they

play in their own organization; as a result, they should give a helping hand to female family members in household activities.

Government

12. The government need to come up with stringent laws and regulations in order to combat the glass ceiling, and reports ought to be gathered from employers about promotions and the justification for them.
13. Ministry of Federal Affairs and General Administration should take proactive action to break the glass ceiling phenomenon base on this research finding.

Researcher

14. Further researcher can study on women's experiences with the Glass Ceiling may be compared across public, commercial, and government sectors.
15. Further researcher can study women hurdle in private organization in Nepalese context.

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Appendix 1: Questionnaire

Glass Ceiling Factors Affecting Women's Career Advancement in the Public Sector of Nepal

Consent Form

Dear Respondents

I am Dr. Dipak Mahat, conducting academic research (Postdoctoral Fellowship) from Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India in Glass Ceiling factors affecting Women's Career Advancement in the Public Sector of Nepal. I would be most grateful if you could voluntarily help me by providing your valuable input for the success of this study. Please be assured that any information provided will be kept strictly confidential. You are entirely free to withdraw at any time or to decline to answer any questions without prejudice.

Please, read all the questions thoroughly and answer / O / Circle the best one in your context.

If you have any queries regarding this study, please call me in my cell phone: 9851164384

मेरो नाम डा.दिपक महत हो । म नेपालको सार्वजनिक क्षेत्रमा महिलाको करियरको उन्नतिलाई असर गर्ने **Glass Ceiling** कारकहरूमा शैक्षिकअनुसन्धान(Postdoctoral Fellowship) भारतको श्रीनिवास विश्वविद्यालय, मंगलौर, कर्नाटकबाट गर्दैछु। यसकालागि म यहाँहरूलाई यो अध्ययनमा सहभागीभएर सहयोग गरी दिनकालागि अनुरोध गर्दछु । तपाईंहरूले दिनु भएको सबै सूचनाहरू गोप्य रहने कुराको अवगत गराउन चाहन्छु । कृपया, सबै प्रश्नहरू पढेर उत्तर दिनको लागि अनुरोध गर्दछु । यहाँहरूलाई यस अध्ययनप्रतिकुनै थपजानकारी चाहिएमा मेरो मोबाइलनं: ९८५११६४३८४ माजुनसुकै बेलापनि सम्पर्क गर्न सक्नु हुनेछ ।

धन्यवाद,

Signature of participants: Date:

Signature of enumerator:

Demographic

SN	Questions	Answer				
1.	Work experience कार्यअनुभव:years					
2.	Education level शिक्षा	1. Bachelor स्नातकतह	2. Master स्नातकोत्तर	3. M.Phil. एम.फिल.	4. PhD पीएचडी	
3	Marital Status वैवाहिकस्थिति	1. Unmarried अविवाहित	2. Married विवाहित	3. Divorce सम्बन्धविच्छेद		
4	Family types पारिवारिकप्रकार	1. Joint familyसंयुक्तपरिवार	2. Singlefamily एकलपरिवार			
5	Job position level कार्यस्थितिस्तर	1. Special class विशिष्टश्रेणी	2. First class प्रथमश्रेणी	3. Second class द्वितीयश्रेणी	4. Third class तृतीयश्रेणी	
6	Age उमेर..... years					
7	Name of the organization/Ministry कार्यरतसंस्था/मन्त्रालयकोनाम:					
SN	Factors	Strongly Agree पूर्णसहमत	Agree सहमत	Neutral तटस्थ	Disagree असहमत	Strongly disagree पूर्णअसहमत
SF8	I see women being repressed in many aspects of society. समाजका विभिन्न पक्षमा महिला उत्पीडित भएको देख्छु।	1	2	3	4	5
SF9	In a mixed-gender workplace, women face a lack of protection and security. मिश्रित लैङ्गिक कार्यस्थलमा, महिलाहरूले सुरक्षा र संरक्षणको अभावको सामना गर्छन्।	1	2	3	4	5
SF10	In our society, women are viewed as having a lower status than males, rather than motivation and empowerment. प्रेरणा र सशक्तिकरण गर्नुको सट्टा हाम्रो समाजमा, महिलाहरूलाई पुरुषको तुलनामा तल्लो स्तरको रूपमा हेरिन्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
SF11	Women's performance in the workplace is regarded as inadequate. कार्यस्थलमा महिलाको कार्यसम्पादन अपर्याप्त मानिन्छ।	1	2	3	4	5

SF12	In our society, women are viewed as unsuitable for higher-level positions. हाम्रो समाजमा महिलालाई उच्च पदका लागि अयोग्य मानिन्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
SF13	In our society, women are regarded to be less committed at workplace. हाम्रो समाजमा महिलालाई कार्यस्थलमा कम प्रतिबद्ध मानिन्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
SF14	Women in our society are more focused on family roles. हाम्रो समाजले महिलालाई पारिवारिक भूमिकामा बढी जोड दिएको छ।	1	2	3	4	5
PF15	Promotions are less important to women. पदोन्नति महिलाहरूको लागि कम महत्वपूर्ण हुन्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
PF16	Women value a well-balanced family life than a well-paid job. महिलाहरूले राम्रो तलबको जागिरभन्दा राम्रो सन्तुलित पारिवारिक जीवनलाई महत्व दिन्छन्।	1	2	3	4	5
PF17	Women are less prepared, in terms of talents or temperament, for higher level position. उच्च पदको लागि, प्रतिभा वा स्वभावको हिसाबले महिलाहरू कम तयार हुन्छन्।	1	2	3	4	5
PF18	Women are unable to work full-time. महिला पूर्ण समय काम गर्न असमर्थ छन्।	1	2	3	4	5
PF19	Women have low self-esteem and lack professional confidence. महिलाहरूमा आत्मसम्मान र व्यावसायिक आत्मविश्वासको कमी छ।	1	2	3	4	5
PF20	Women are underqualified for certain jobs. महिलाहरू निश्चित कामहरूको लागि कम योग्य छन्।	1	2	3	4	5
PF21	Women are reluctant to accept responsibility. महिलाहरू जिम्मेवारी स्वीकार गर्न हिचकिचाउँछन्।	1	2	3	4	5
PF22	Women have Lack of mental and health issues at work place. महिलालाई कार्यस्थलमा मानसिक र स्वास्थ्य समस्याहरू छन्।	1	2	3	4	5
WE23	Women have not been assigned challenge/high visibility projects. महिलाहरूलाई चुनौती/उच्च दृश्यता परियोजनाहरू तोकिएको छैन।	1	2	3	4	5
WE24	Women's Competitiveness with male is regards as a negative trait. पुरुषसँग महिलाको प्रतिस्पर्धालाई नकारात्मक रूपमा लिइन्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
WE25	Male contemporaries' friends are not ready to accept women at high job position. पुरुष समकालीन साथीहरू महिलालाई उच्च पदमा स्वीकार गर्न तयार छैनन्।	1	2	3	4	5
WE26	When women hold senior positions, male employees feel uneasy to work. महिला उच्च पदमा बस्दा, पुरुष कर्मचारीहरूले काम गर्न असहज महसूस गर्छन्।	1	2	3	4	5
WE27	Male employees having strong networks than female. महिलाभन्दा पुरुष कर्मचारीको सञ्जाल बलियो हुन्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
WE28	If women ready to handle higher position she have to face Isolation at work. महिला उच्च पद सम्हाल्न तयार भएमा काममा एक्लोपनको सामना गर्नुपर्ने हुन्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
OF29	Women's progress and gender equality are not prioritized by organization. महिलाको प्रगति र लैङ्गिक समानतालाई संगठनले प्राथमिकतामा राखेको छैन।	1	2	3	4	5
OF30	Women receive fewer opportunities for professional development at work. महिलाहरूले काममा व्यावसायिक विकासका लागि कम अवसरहरू पाउँछन्।	1	2	3	4	5

OF31	A woman must perform better than a man to be promoted. पदोन्नतिको लागि पुरुषभन्दा महिलाले राम्रो प्रदर्शन गर्नुपर्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
OF32	Organizational policies that encourage women's professional advancement are lacking. महिलाहरूको व्यावसायिक उन्नतिलाई प्रोत्साहन गर्ने संगठनात्मक नीतिहरूको अभाव छ।	1	2	3	4	5
OF33	Women are underrepresented in the policy making process. नीति निर्माण प्रक्रियामा महिलाहरूको प्रतिनिधित्व कम हुन्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
OF34	Male hierarchies are more inclined to elevate males to positions of leadership. नेतृत्वदायी पदका लागि पुरुषहरूलाई बढावा दिने सम्भावना बढी हुन्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
OF35	Women face a lack of mentorship and managerial training at work place. महिलाहरूले मार्गदर्शन र व्यवस्थापकीय तालिमको अभावको सामना गर्छन्।	1	2	3	4	5
OF36	Women's career advancement is hampered by an inhospitable workplace culture. आतिथ्यविहीन संगठनात्मक संस्कृतिले महिलाको वृत्ति विकासको लागि बाधाको रूपमा काम गर्दछ।	1	2	3	4	5
FF37	My career is not important due to primary focus to family. परिवारमा मुख्य ध्यान केन्द्रित भएकाले मेरो वृत्ति विकास महत्त्वपूर्ण छैन।	1	2	3	4	5
FF38	Taking care of my family is a hindrance to my career growth. मेरो परिवारको हेरचाह गर्नु मेरो करियरको विकासमा बाधा हो।	1	2	3	4	5
FF39	It is tough to strike a balance between family matters and professional commitments. पारिवारिक मामिला र पेशागत प्रतिबद्धताहरू बीच सन्तुलन मिलाउन गाह्रो छ।	1	2	3	4	5
FF40	If I don't spend enough time with my family, I feel bad. यदि मैले मेरो परिवारसँग पर्याप्त समय बिताउन सकिन भने, मलाई नराम्रो लाग्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
FF41	I'm prepared to avoid family responsibilities to advance in job. म काममा अगाडि बढ्नको लागि पारिवारिक जिम्मेवारीबाट पन्छिन तयार छु।	1	2	3	4	5
FF42	More job responsibilities have a bad effect on my family life. धेरै कामको जिम्मेवारीले मेरो पारिवारिक जीवनमा नराम्रो प्रभाव पार्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
FF43	I would not take a high position if my family would not assist me with housework. यदि मेरो परिवारले मलाई घराएसी कामकाजमा सहयोग नगरेको भए म उच्च पद लिन सकिदैन।	1	2	3	4	5
FF44	My dedication to family life is a hindrance to my professional advancement. पारिवारिक जीवनमा मेरो समर्पण मेरो पेशागत व्यावसायिक उन्नतिको लागि बाधक हो।	1	2	3	4	5
FF45	I would not have earned a better higher level job if I hadn't been committed to my family members. यदि म मेरो परिवारका सदस्यहरूप्रति प्रतिबद्ध नभएको भए मैले राम्रो उच्च पदको काम पाउने थिइन।	1	2	3	4	5

CF46	Cultural beliefs are not hostile to women career advancement. सांस्कृतिक विश्वास महिला वृत्ति विकासको लागि प्रतिकूल छैन।	1	2	3	4	5
CF47	Men dislike sharing power with women. पुरुषलाई महिलासँग शक्ति बाँड्न मन पर्दैन।	1	2	3	4	5
CF48	Women's traditional status as a weaker gender has a negative impact on their job advancement. कमजोर लिंगको रूपमा महिलाहरूको परम्परागत स्थितिले उनीहरूको कामको उन्नतिमा नकारात्मक असर पार्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
CF49	Culture restrict women from move ability (night meeting, conference, seminar) during work. मेरो संस्कृतिले कामको क्रममा महिलाहरूलाई कार्य समय देखि बाहेक अतिरिक्त समयमा हिँडडुल (रातको बैठक, सम्मेलन, सेमिनार) गर्न प्रतिबन्धित छ।	1	2	3	4	5
CF50	I feel discriminated against as a woman because of my gender. म महिला भएको कारणले भेदभाव महसूस गर्छु।	1	2	3	4	5
CF51	Working outside the house is against cultural conventions for a woman. घरबाहिर काम गर्नु महिलाका लागि सांस्कृतिक परम्पराको विरुद्ध हो।	1	2	3	4	5
CA52	Women have no plenty of opportunity to progress to top higher positions in my organization. महिलाहरूलाई मेरो कम्पनीमा शीर्ष व्यवस्थापन पदहरूमा प्रगति गर्ने प्रशस्त अवसरहरू छैन।	1	2	3	4	5
CA53	Men and women have no equal opportunity for career advancement in my organization. मेरो संगठनमा करियरको प्रगतिको लागि पुरुष र महिला समान अवसरहरू छैन।	1	2	3	4	5
CA54	A woman cannot become a Higher level administrator in the future, according to the way my organization functions. मेरो कम्पनीको काम गर्ने तरिका अनुसार भविष्यमा महिला वरिष्ठ प्रबन्धक बन्न सक्दैनन्।	1	2	3	4	5
CA55	In my organization, men and women are treated unequally. मेरो संस्थामा पुरुष र महिलालाई असमान व्यवहार गरिन्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
CA56	In my organization, less number of women climbing the corporate ladder and obtaining higher positions. मेरो संगठनमा नेतृत्वदायी पदमा चढ्ने र उच्च पदहरू प्राप्त गर्ने महिलाहरूको संख्या कम छ।	1	2	3	4	5
CA57	In my organization, Women are discouraged to apply for higher level positions. मेरो संस्थामा, उच्च व्यवस्थापकीय पदका लागि आवेदन दिन महिलाहरूलाई निरुत्साहित गरिन्छ।	1	2	3	4	5
CA58	In my organization, the men's network hinders women's possibilities for advancement to higher positions. मेरो संगठनमा, पुरुषहरूको नेटवर्कले उच्च स्थानहरूमा उन्नतिको लागि महिलाहरूको सम्भावनालाई बाधा पुऱ्याउँछ।	1	2	3	4	5
CA59	In my organization, women have to perform better than their male counterparts to be promoted to the same position. मेरो संस्थामा, समान पदमा बढुवा गर्न महिलाहरूले	1	2	3	4	5

आफना पुरुष समकक्षहरू भन्दा राम्रो प्रदर्शन गर्नुपर्छ।					
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60. Have you experienced any gender/age/education/position/marital status related artificial barriers, which influenced your Career advancement? Please describe के तपाईंले कुनै लिंग/उमेर/शिक्षा/कार्यस्थिति/वैवाहिक स्थिति सम्बन्धित बनावटी अवरोधहरू अनुभव गर्नुभएको छ, जसले तपाईंको करियरको उन्नतिलाई प्रभाव पारेको छ? कृपया वर्णन गर्नुहोस्

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61. In your opinions, what are the main problems that women have to face in advancing to higher level hierarchy roles? Explainतपाईंको विचारमा, उच्च स्तरको पदानुक्रम भूमिकामा अगाडि बढ्न महिलाहरूले सामना गर्नुपर्ने मुख्य समस्याहरू के के हुन्?व्याख्या गर्नुहोस्

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62. What advice would you give for breaking the glass ceiling to uplift women career?महिलाको करियरलाई प्रवर्द्धनको लागि, बनावटी अवरोधहरू (Glass Ceiling) तोड्नके सल्लाह दिनुहुन्छ?

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63. If you have any Suggestion regarding Glass Ceiling, please explain?यदि तपाईं सँग महिलाको करियर लिएर बनावटी अवरोधहरूको बारेमा कुनै सुझाव छ भने कृपया व्याख्या गर्नुहोस्?

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Thank You

Appendix 2: Interview Questions

Demographic factors on women's career advancement

1. Have you experienced any gender related bias which as influenced your Career advancement? Please describe
2. Do you think required Education level influence your career advancement? How
3. Does your career advancement affect by marital status (Unmarried/married/Divorce)? Describe
4. Do your Family types (Nuclear/joint) affect your career growth? Explain
5. Do you think level of job position encourage you for making career growth?
6. Do you think age factors play vital role in women's career advancement? How

Barriers that stop women from advancing to higher-level administration roles

7. What are the main reasons that women have to for advancing to higher level hierarchy roles?
8. In your opinion does societal factors stop you from advancing to a senior position? In what way
9. Have you notice Personal factors that stop women for career advancement? Explain
10. Do you believe that Organizational factor impact on your professional advancement? How
11. Have you ever had to deal with family issues that stop women from advancing in their careers? Explain
12. What do you think about Cultural Factors does it affect your career advancement? How
13. Do you feel working environment affect you career advancement? How

Effective model to break class ceiling.

14. What advice would you give for breaking the glass ceiling to uplift career?

Appendix 3: Publications List

Mahat, D., & Aithal, P. S. (2022). Women's Articulates towards Career Advancement. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences*, 7(1), 417-424.[CrossRef](#)

Mahat, D., & Aithal, P. S. (2022). Socio-culture and Women Career Development: References to Government Agencies of Nepal. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences*, 7(2), 241-249.[CrossRef](#)